

*Next-to-Next-to-Leading Order Real-Virtual
Corrections to Soft Functions
with Massive Partons*

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Introduction

The pursuit of all scientific workings is to describe nature in the best possible way and make precise predictions that can be experimentally verified. There is arguably no better example of such efforts, be it theory or experiment, than high energy physics. With experimental setups that span over many kilometres just to be able to measure the finest structure of the universe, and incredibly precise theories that go hand in hand, it is the pinnacle of modern fundamental physics. But as much of an engineering challenge as constructing such experiments over vastly different scales is, theoretical particle physics itself also has to deal with problems that arise, if collider processes involve disparate scales Λ . These difficulties become more and more apparent the higher the order in perturbative calculations and involve large logarithms of the form $\ln\left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{high}}}{\Lambda_{\text{low}}}\right)$ that spoil the perturbation series. These logarithms would make it impossible to reach the precision needed for finding deviations of the Standard Model of particle physics (SM) and thus maybe new, unknown particles that could be the stepping stone to describing phenomena like dark matter.

A useful tool for dealing with such challenges in general are effective theories, which can come in all kinds of different forms. In this thesis specifically, we will be dealing with Soft-Collinear Effective Theory (SCET) (see Ref. [1]) which is used to resolve aforementioned multiscale problems arising because of massless particles that are deeply embedded in the SM.

We will start by giving a brief introduction to the SM and Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) with all its important aspects, before talking about the method of regions and effective field theories (EFTs) as well as going into much more detail in terms of SCET specifically. Our presentation of the method of regions and SCET is just an abstract of the much more detailed lecture notes that can be found in Ref. [2] and follows along the same lines. At the very end of chapter 3, we will see that cross sections factorize into different functions (see Ref. [3]) that each depend only on one of the many scales involved in the process. While all these functions are needed to determine cross sections, they are each very complex objects in their own right, and it is only the so-called soft function we will consider in this thesis. It contains all the soft, that is low energetic, QCD radiation, and it can be calculated order by order in perturbation theory. So far, it has been automated for various observables up to next-to-next-to leading order (NNLO) in the massless case (see Ref. [4]) and up to NLO in the massive case (see Ref. [5]). Furthermore, there are already some analytic results for the real-virtual part of the NNLO soft function involving massive quarks (see Refs. [6] and [7]) that can be used as a check for our calculations. In this thesis, we will focus our attention purely on the two-particle correlations of the NNLO real-virtual soft function and automate these calculations for a general SCET-1 observable.

Ultimately, the aim is to calculate the total NNLO soft function for hadronic $t\bar{t}$ production, resum the previously mentioned Sudakov logarithms with the help of renormalization group equations (RGEs) up to next-to-next-to logarithmic (NNLL') accuracy and make use of the GENEVA Monte Carlo framework (see Ref. [8]) to match theoretical predictions for hadronic $t\bar{t}$ -production to measurements at the ATLAS and CMS experiments. Because of their high mass, having precise knowledge of top quark physics, as it is predicted in the SM, plays a vital role in finding new, heavy particles beyond the SM (BSM).

Quantum Chromodynamics and Infrared Divergences

2.1 Standard Model of Particle Physics

The Standard Model of Particle Physics (SM) is an astounding success and result of decades-long work by many great physicists in the twentieth century. It describes three of the four fundamental forces in the universe, namely electrodynamics as well as the strong and weak nuclear force, and it has so far even withstood rigorous testing by extremely precise measurements with more than ten significant figures of accuracy (see Ref. [9]). While it is the most precisely tested theory of all time, it still has its flaws. It does not include a description of gravity or dark matter, and requires a substantial amount of numerical constants and fine-tuning. Most particle physicists therefore believe that the SM is most likely just an effective theory, and that there is physics beyond the SM (BSM) that has yet to be found. Finding BSM particles will require an excellent understanding of high energy physics, as it is predicted by the SM and very precise measurements at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and other colliders.

Mathematically, the SM is based on a theory of field operators (see Ref. [11])

$$\phi(x) = \int \frac{d^3p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{2p^0} \left(e^{-ip \cdot x} a(p) + e^{ip \cdot x} a^\dagger(p) \right), \quad (2.1)$$

$$\psi_\alpha(x) = \sum_s \int \frac{d^3p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{2p^0} \left(u_\alpha(p, s) e^{-ip \cdot x} a(p, s) + v_\alpha(p, s) e^{ip \cdot x} b^\dagger(p, s) \right), \quad (2.2)$$

$$A^\mu(x) = \sum_\sigma \int \frac{d^3p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{2p^0} \left(\varepsilon^\mu(p, \sigma) e^{-ip \cdot x} a(p, \sigma) + \varepsilon^\mu(p, \sigma)^* e^{ip \cdot x} a^\dagger(p, \sigma) \right), \quad (2.3)$$

etc.,

with creation and annihilation operators $a^{(\dagger)}$ and $b^{(\dagger)}$, that define any possible quantized field configuration at space-time coordinate x and thus the physical state $|p_1, \dots, p_N\rangle$ of all N elementary particles in the system. Quantum field theories are the result of combining quantum mechanics with special relativity and its Lorentz-invariant properties.

Transformation properties under different symmetry groups specify the structure (local symmetries) and give rise to conservation laws (global symmetries). The theory consists of 37 such particles (see Figure 2.1) that can be split into leptons and quarks – which each have three different generations – their associated antiparticles, twelve gauge bosons – including eight different gluons – and the Higgs boson.

Figure 2.1: All elementary particles included in the Standard Model with their respective mass, charge and spin¹⁰.

All of these particles have their own characteristic rest mass, strong and electric charge as well as their spin. Leptons and quarks are massive fermions – spin-1/2 particles – that can interact with each other by exchanging force-carrying gauge bosons. While the massless photon couples to all electrically charged particles, the gluons mediate the force between all colour charged particles, including themselves. The W^{\pm} - and Z -boson are responsible for the charged and neutral weak currents respectively that cause weak decay and mixing between different quark and lepton flavours. After the Higgs boson was finally experimentally verified in 2012 [12], the SM had found its already anticipated spin-0 boson giving mass to all matter particles and the weak gauge bosons in a process called spontaneous symmetry breaking.

A formalism called path integrals, which was developed during the first half of the twentieth century and brought to completion by Richard Feynman in 1948¹³, involves the Lagrangian density $\mathcal{L}(\phi, \psi, \dots)$ and can be used to calculate cross sections of collision events for example by way of perturbation theory. These calculations lead to Feynman diagrams that can be depicted as fundamental interaction vertices connected to lines corresponding to real or virtual particles that are being exchanged.

A general cross section for $pp \rightarrow X$ can be written as (see Ref. [14])

$$\sigma = \sum_{i,j} \int dx_1 \int dx_2 f_i(x_1, \mu) f_j(x_2, \mu) \hat{\sigma}_{ij \rightarrow X}(x_1, x_2, \mu), \quad (2.4)$$

with the parton distribution functions (PDFs) f_k and the renormalized, partonic cross section $\hat{\sigma}_{ij \rightarrow X}$.

2.2 Strong Interaction

As previously mentioned, it is the underlying local symmetry that defines the structure of a quantum field theory. These symmetries are in fact required when the theory involves massless spin-1 particles like the gluon or photon. In the case of the strong interaction consisting of quarks and gluons, that symmetry group is called special unitary group $SU(3)$, or more general $SU(N)$, and the theory is called quantum chromodynamics (QCD).

To construct a Lagrangian density invariant under $SU(N)$ transformations, it is necessary to first specify how the fields themselves transform (see Ref. [15]). Quark fields $\psi(x)$ are supposed to transform in the three-dimensional fundamental representation of the $SU(3)$. An infinitesimal transformation of any quark field operator then takes the form

$$\psi'_a(x) = \left(\mathbf{1}_{ab} + i\kappa^A(x)T_{ab}^A \right) \psi_b(x), \quad (2.5)$$

where T_{ab}^A are generators of the Lie algebra given by the Gell-Mann matrices and each entry of ψ consists of a four-component Dirac spinor:

$$\psi(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_{\text{red}}(x) \\ \psi_{\text{green}}(x) \\ \psi_{\text{blue}}(x) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.6)$$

There are also eight different gluon field operators $A_\mu^A(x)$ which transform in a more complicated way because they are part of a covariant derivative

$$D_{\mu,ab} = \partial_\mu \delta_{ab} - igA_\mu^A(x)T_{ab}^A, \quad (2.7)$$

transforming like the quark field operators, and the field-strength tensor

$$G_{\mu\nu}^A(x) = G_{\mu\nu}^A(x)T^A = \frac{i}{g} [D_\mu, D_\nu] = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu - ig [A_\mu, A_\nu], \quad (2.8)$$

transforming in the adjoint representation

$$G_{\mu\nu}^{\prime A} = \left(\mathbf{1}^{AB} + i\kappa^C(x) \left(T_{\text{adj.}}^C \right)^{AB} \right) G_{\mu\nu}^B. \quad (2.9)$$

The QCD Lagrangian density can then be written in the compact form

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{4}G_{\mu\nu}^A G^{A,\mu\nu} + \bar{\psi} (i\not{D} - m) \psi, \quad (2.10)$$

containing the kinetic terms of free propagation as well as the interaction between quarks and gluons, and two different expressions describing cubic and quartic interactions of gluons with each other.

Due to the two unphysical degrees of freedom left in the four dimensional gluon field operators when working in a Lorentz invariant Lorenz gauge $\partial_\mu A^\mu(x) = 0$, more expressions have to be added to

2.2. Strong Interaction

the Lagrangian density, counteracting double counting that would otherwise arise in the path integral formalism [16]:

$$\mathcal{L}_{FP} = -\frac{1}{2\xi} \left(\partial^\mu A_\mu^A \right)^2 + \left(\partial^\mu \bar{\omega}^A \right) \partial_\mu \omega^A - gf^{ABC} \left(\partial^\mu \bar{\omega}^A \right) \omega^B A_\mu^C. \quad (2.11)$$

These expressions add new unphysical and purely virtual Faddeev-Popov ghost fields, ω^A and $\bar{\omega}^A$, that interact with gluons.

The Feynman rules of unrenormalized QCD are (see Ref. [15]):

$$\begin{aligned} \beta, b \text{ --- } p \text{ --- } \alpha, a &= \frac{i(\not{p} + m)_{\alpha\beta}}{p^2 - m^2 + i0} \delta_{ab}, & A \text{ --- } k \text{ --- } B &= \frac{i}{k^2 + i0} \delta^{AB}, \\ \mu, A \text{ --- } \alpha, a &= ig\gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\mu T_{ab}^A, & \mu, B \text{ --- } C &= -gf^{ABC} p^\mu, \\ \mu, A \text{ --- } p &= \frac{-ig^{\mu\nu}}{p^2 + i0} \delta^{AB}, & p, \sigma \text{ --- } \mu, A &= \varepsilon_\mu^A(p, \sigma), \\ \mu, A \text{ --- } p, \sigma &= [\varepsilon_\mu^A(p, \sigma)]^*, & p, s \text{ --- } \alpha, a &= u_\alpha^a(p, s), \\ \alpha, a \text{ --- } p, s &= \bar{u}_\alpha^a(p, s), & p, s \text{ --- } \alpha, a &= \bar{v}_\alpha^a(p, s), \\ \alpha, a \text{ --- } p, s &= v_\alpha^a(p, s), & & \\ \nu, B & & & \\ \mu, A \text{ --- } p &= gf^{ABC} [g^{\mu\nu}(k-p)^\rho + g^{\nu\rho}(p-q)^\mu + g^{\rho\mu}(q-k)^\nu], & & \\ \rho, C & & & \\ \mu, A \text{ --- } \sigma, D & & & \\ \nu, B \text{ --- } \rho, C &= -ig^2 \left[\begin{aligned} & f^{ABE} f^{CDE} (g_{\mu\rho} g_{\nu\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma} g_{\nu\rho}) \\ & + f^{ACE} f^{BDE} (g_{\mu\nu} g_{\rho\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma} g_{\nu\rho}) \\ & + f^{ADE} f^{BCE} (g_{\mu\nu} g_{\rho\sigma} - g_{\mu\rho} g_{\nu\sigma}) \end{aligned} \right], & (2.12) \end{aligned}$$

with the vector field polarisation ε_μ^A as well as spinor components v_α^a and u_α^a . The dashed lines correspond to ghost fields, wiggly lines correspond to gluons, and the solid lines correspond to quarks. Momentum conservation is fulfilled at each vertex, and all unknown loop momenta have to be integrated over.

2.3 Renormalization

Most of the one- or higher-loop diagrams are ultraviolet divergent and can therefore not be used when computing physical observables, such as cross sections, without first being dealt with in a procedure called renormalization. Renormalizing the bare fields ψ , A^μ , etc. as well as the bare coupling g and mass m is required anyway, as can be seen when calculating the full propagator in an interacting QFT that always includes a cloud of virtual particles (see Ref. [17]). This definition of the pole mass and on-shell field operator is connected to the bare objects via a divergent relation that exactly cancels out the UV divergences of the loop diagrams.

In general, the process of renormalizing a quantum field theory is very abstract and there are many different ways of defining renormalized fields, couplings and masses that can however all be linked with each other by a finite renormalization scheme. The approach is always to first regularize the divergences in the loop integrals, e.g. by switching the integral from four to $d = 4 - 2\varepsilon$ dimensions

$$\int \frac{d^4k}{(2\pi)^4} \rightarrow \int \frac{d^d k}{(2\pi)^d}, \quad (2.13)$$

choosing a renormalization scheme and then rewriting the bare parameters in terms of renormalized parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &= \sqrt{Z_\psi} \psi_r, & A^{A,\mu} &= \sqrt{Z_A} A_r^{A,\mu}, \\ m &= Z_m m_r, & \xi &= Z_\xi \xi_r, \\ g &= \left(\underbrace{\sqrt{\frac{e^{\gamma_E}}{4\pi}} \mu}_{\tilde{\mu}} \right)^\varepsilon Z_g g_r, & \omega^A &= \sqrt{Z_\omega} \omega_r^A, \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

with the renormalization scale μ being introduced to maintain the mass dimensions of the renormalized coupling constant.

The expressions in the Lagrangian density are then split into two parts in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\psi} (i\mathcal{D} - m) \psi &= \bar{\psi}_r (i\underline{\mathcal{D}}_r - m_r) \psi_r + \left[i (Z_\psi - 1) \bar{\psi}_r \not{\partial} \psi_r - (Z_m Z_\psi - 1) m_r \bar{\psi}_r \psi_r \right. \\ &\quad \left. - g_r \left(\tilde{\mu}^\varepsilon Z_g Z_\psi \sqrt{Z_A} - 1 \right) \bar{\psi}_r A_r^A T^A \psi_r \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

While the underlined term just results in Feynman rules already mentioned in Eq. (2.12), with the only difference being renormalized parameters, the other terms lead to new, so called counter term

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Feynman rules (see Ref. [15]):

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 1} \\ \text{Diagram 2} \\ \text{Diagram 3} \\ \text{Diagram 4} \end{array} \right) = (\tilde{\mu}^\varepsilon Z_g Z_\omega \sqrt{Z_A} - 1) \times \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 1} \\ \text{Diagram 2} \\ \text{Diagram 3} \\ \text{Diagram 4} \end{array} \right), \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 5} \\ \text{Diagram 6} \end{array} \right) = (\tilde{\mu}^{2\varepsilon} Z_g^2 Z_A^2 - 1) \times \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 5} \\ \text{Diagram 6} \end{array} \right), \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 7} \\ \text{Diagram 8} \end{array} \right) = (\tilde{\mu}^\varepsilon Z_g Z_A^{3/2} - 1) \times \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 7} \\ \text{Diagram 8} \end{array} \right), \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 9} \end{array} \right) = (\tilde{\mu}^\varepsilon Z_g Z_\psi \sqrt{Z_A} - 1) \times \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram 9} \end{array} \right), \\
 & \mu, A \otimes \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{p} \\ \text{---} \end{array} \otimes \nu, B = -i \left[(Z_A - 1)(p^2 g^{\mu\nu} - p^\mu p^\nu) + \left(\frac{Z_A}{\tilde{\mu}^\varepsilon Z_g} - 1 \right) \frac{1}{\xi} p^\mu p^\nu \right] \delta^{AB}, \\
 & \beta, b \otimes \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{p} \\ \text{---} \end{array} \otimes \alpha, a = i \left[(Z_\psi - 1) \not{p} - (Z_\psi Z_m - 1) m \right]_{\alpha\beta} \delta_{ab}, \\
 & A \otimes \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{k} \\ \text{---} \end{array} \otimes B = i(Z_\omega - 1) k^2 \delta^{AB}. \tag{2.16}
 \end{aligned}$$

The most common renormalization scheme, that will also be used in this thesis, is called modified

minimal subtraction (\overline{MS}) scheme, and takes the form:

$$\alpha = \frac{g^2}{4\pi} = \left(\frac{e^{\gamma_E}}{4\pi} \mu^2 \right)^\varepsilon Z_\alpha \alpha_r, \quad \text{with} \quad Z_\alpha = 1 - \underbrace{\left(\frac{11}{3}C_A - \frac{4}{3}T_F n_f \right)}_{\beta_0} \frac{\alpha_r}{4\pi\varepsilon}. \quad (2.17)$$

Since the renormalization scale μ was an arbitrary factor stemming from dimensional regularization, the dependencies in $\alpha_r(\mu)$ should exactly cancel out any dependencies of μ in the relation between bare and renormalized parameters, leaving the bare coupling to be independent of μ . This fact then leads to a differential equation called the renormalization group equation (RGE):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\alpha}{d(\ln \mu)} &= 2\varepsilon \tilde{\mu}^{2\varepsilon} Z_\alpha \alpha_r + \tilde{\mu}^{2\varepsilon} \frac{dZ_\alpha}{d(\ln \mu)} \alpha_r + \tilde{\mu}^{2\varepsilon} Z_\alpha \frac{d\alpha_r}{d(\ln \mu)} = 0. \\ \Rightarrow \frac{d\alpha_r}{d(\ln \mu)} &= -2\varepsilon \alpha_r - \underbrace{\frac{1}{Z_\alpha} \frac{dZ_\alpha}{d(\ln \mu)}}_{\beta(\alpha_r)} \alpha_r. \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

RGEs like this exist for all renormalized objects and can be solved order by order in perturbation

Figure 2.2: Running of the strong coupling constant as a function of the energy scale Q ¹⁸.

theory. Since the coupling constant depends on the renormalization scale μ , perturbation theory, which breaks down for a large coupling, is not possible for all values of μ . In QCD the coupling constant decreases monotonically as a function of μ (see Figure 2.2). In addition, cross sections contain Sudakov-logarithms of the form $\ln^{2n} \left(\frac{s}{\mu^2} \right)$ for each $\mathcal{O}(\alpha_r^n)$, with s being the center-of-mass energy, that become very large for small values of μ . When the center-of-mass energy is very high, solving the RGE order by order is not enough and these large logarithms have to be resummed for all orders in α_r by effective field theory techniques.

2.4 Infrared divergences

In a QFT containing massless particles, other divergences occur that cannot be removed by a renormalization program. The origin of these divergences does not lie in the high energy regions of the integrals, but rather in the parts where massless particles are either aligned with other particles (collinear) or have very small energies (soft). However, similar to the UV case, infrared divergences also disappear when physically meaningful, observable quantities like cross sections are calculated. Diagrams with final states containing only quarks or leptons cannot be distinguished from final states that additionally contain massless particles that are very low energetic or travelling in the same direction as the fermions. It turns out that when added together, infrared (IR) divergences of both the real emission and virtual diagrams exactly cancel each other to give a finite answer for every order in perturbation theory.

2.4.1 Method of regions and light-cone coordinates

Figure 2.3: Feynman diagram of a one-loop vertex correction used in the Sudakov form factor.

One way to deal with infrared divergences, called method of regions, is to split the integral in different singular sections, regularize them, and then add all contributions together. An example that is often used to illustrate this strategy is the one-loop Sudakov form factor, as can be seen in Figure 2.3. Neglecting the detailed description of the particles' spin and setting the masses of all internal propagators to zero, one arrives at the following loop integral:

$$I = i\pi^{-\frac{d}{2}} \mu^{2\epsilon} \int d^d k \frac{1}{(k^2 + i0) [(k+l)^2 + i0] [(k+p)^2 + i0]}. \quad (2.19)$$

Because of the fact that it is an off-shell diagram, there are no IR-divergences and we could immediately set $d = 4$ and get the result:

$$I = \frac{1}{Q^2} \left(\ln \frac{Q^2}{L^2} \ln \frac{Q^2}{P^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{3} \right), \quad \text{with } -Q^2 = (p-l)^2, \quad -P^2 = p^2, \quad -L^2 = l^2. \quad (2.20)$$

However, this result can also be reproduced by first splitting the integral into different regions and integrating them separately. Instead of introducing certain cut-offs and integrating only over the relevant regions, it is actually possible to regularize all integrals by switching to $d = 4 - 2\varepsilon$ dimensions and integrate over the full phase space. There will be no double counting, since all integrands scale differently in each region. To make this scaling explicit, it is useful to introduce light-cone coordinates

$$n = (1, 0, 0, 1), \quad \bar{n} = (1, 0, 0, -1), \quad (2.21)$$

with

$$n^2 = \bar{n}^2 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad n \cdot \bar{n} = 2, \quad (2.22)$$

which can now be used to decompose any four-vector into three parts:

$$p^\mu = \underbrace{(n \cdot p) \frac{\bar{n}^\mu}{2}}_{p_+^\mu} + \underbrace{(\bar{n} \cdot p) \frac{n^\mu}{2}}_{p_-^\mu} + p_\perp^\mu. \quad (2.23)$$

The scalar product of two four-vectors can then be written as

$$p \cdot q = p_+ \cdot q_- + p_- \cdot q_+ + p_\perp \cdot q_\perp \quad (2.24)$$

and it is convenient to use the following notation:

$$p = \left(\underbrace{+}_{(n \cdot p)}, \underbrace{-}_{(\bar{n} \cdot p)}, \perp \right). \quad (2.25)$$

Additionally one needs to introduce a small, expansion parameter λ which specifies the exact scaling of the plus, minus and perpendicular component of different momentum vectors in each region:

$$\lambda^2 \sim \frac{P^2}{Q^2} \sim \frac{L^2}{Q^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p^2 \sim l^2 \sim \lambda^2 Q^2, \quad (2.26)$$

with

$$L^2 \equiv -l^2 - i0, \quad P^2 \equiv -p^2 - i0, \quad Q^2 \equiv -(l-p)^2 - i0, \quad (2.27)$$

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and

$$p \sim (\lambda^2, 1, \lambda)Q, \quad l \sim (1, \lambda^2, \lambda)Q. \quad (2.28)$$

We are thus considering a system in which the external legs carry a lot of energy, but their invariant mass is small. The loop momentum k^μ can of course have all kinds of scalings corresponding to different regions of the original phase space, but it can be shown that only four such scalings give rise to non-vanishing contributions to the final result:

1. Hard region: $k \sim (1, 1, 1)Q$,
2. Region collinear to p (c): $k \sim (\lambda^2, 1, \lambda)Q$,
3. Region collinear to l (\bar{c}): $k \sim (1, \lambda^2, \lambda)Q$,
4. Soft region: $k \sim (\lambda^2, \lambda^2, \lambda^2)Q$.

Let us first consider the hard region and calculate all terms in the denominator up to leading power in λ :

$$\begin{aligned} k^2 &\sim \lambda^0 Q^2, \\ (k+l)^2 &= \underbrace{k^2}_{\mathcal{O}(\lambda^0)} + 2(\underbrace{k_+ \cdot l_-}_{\mathcal{O}(\lambda^2)} + \underbrace{k_- \cdot l_+}_{\mathcal{O}(\lambda^0)} + \underbrace{k_\perp \cdot l_\perp}_{\mathcal{O}(\lambda)}) + \underbrace{l^2}_{\mathcal{O}(\lambda^2)} = k^2 + 2k_- \cdot l_+ + \mathcal{O}(\lambda), \\ (k+p)^2 &= \dots = k^2 + 2k_+ \cdot p_- + \mathcal{O}(\lambda). \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

Going back now to the integral in Eq. (2.19) and inserting the expansion, we arrive at:

$$\begin{aligned} I_h &= i\pi^{-\frac{d}{2}} \mu^{2\varepsilon} \int d^d k \frac{1}{(k^2 + i0) [k^2 + 2k_- \cdot l_+ + i0] [k^2 + 2k_+ \cdot p_- + i0]} \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)}{Q^2} \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \ln \frac{\mu^2}{Q^2} + \frac{1}{2} \ln^2 \frac{\mu^2}{Q^2} - \frac{\pi^2}{6} + \mathcal{O}(\lambda) \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (2.30)$$

Similarly the denominators of the three other regions can be expanded, keeping in mind the different scalings of k , and one finds:

$$\begin{aligned} I_c &= i\pi^{-\frac{d}{2}}\mu^{2\varepsilon} \int d^d k \frac{1}{(k^2 + i0) [2k_- \cdot l_+ + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^2) + i0] [(k+p)^2 + i0]} \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)}{Q^2} \left(-\frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} - \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \ln \frac{\mu^2}{P^2} - \frac{1}{2} \ln^2 \frac{\mu^2}{P^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{6} + \mathcal{O}(\lambda) \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon), \end{aligned} \quad (2.31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\bar{c}} &= i\pi^{-\frac{d}{2}}\mu^{2\varepsilon} \int d^d k \frac{1}{(k^2 + i0) [(k+l)^2 + i0] [2k_+ \cdot p_- + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^2) + i0]} \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)}{Q^2} \left(-\frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} - \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \ln \frac{\mu^2}{L^2} - \frac{1}{2} \ln^2 \frac{\mu^2}{L^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{6} + \mathcal{O}(\lambda) \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon), \end{aligned} \quad (2.32)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_s &= i\pi^{-\frac{d}{2}}\mu^{2\varepsilon} \int d^d k \frac{1}{(k^2 + i0) [2k_- \cdot l_+ + l^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3) + i0] [2k_+ \cdot p_- + p^2 + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^3) + i0]} \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)}{Q^2} \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \ln \frac{\mu^2 Q^2}{L^2 P^2} + \frac{1}{2} \ln^2 \frac{\mu^2 Q^2}{L^2 P^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{6} + \mathcal{O}(\lambda) \right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (2.33)$$

When summing up all integrals, we can see that the poles in ε vanish and we end up with a finite result of the form:

$$I = I_h + I_p + I_l + I_s = \frac{1}{Q^2} \left(\ln \frac{Q^2}{L^2} \ln \frac{Q^2}{P^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{3} + \mathcal{O}(\lambda) \right). \quad (2.34)$$

At this stage, it should be pointed out that even though the divergence in I_h is of infrared origin, it exactly cancels out the ultraviolet divergences of both the collinear and soft integrals. However, this cancellation is different from the one between real emission and virtual diagrams, as mentioned earlier, because it involved an IR-safe, off-shell diagram. The divergences were only a result of splitting the integral into different kinematic regions which can be interpreted by an effective field theory approach, as we will see in the next chapter. A detailed discussion about the vanishing overlaps between different regions as well as the cancellation of both types of divergences can be found in Ref. [2].

Soft-Collinear Effective Theory

3.1 Basic concept of an effective field theory

Effective field theories (EFTs) are a way to describe interactions involving different scales. They exist in many forms and can be built from bottom up as an approximation, for example when the underlying theory is not fully understood, or from top down in cases where factorization and resummation procedures are necessary to achieve useful theoretical predictions. While the SM and Fermi's theory of beta decay were built from the bottom up, Soft-collinear effective theory (SCET) for instance is built from top down.

In both cases, the idea is to construct a Lagrangian density out of generally non-local, symmetry invariant operators $O_i(x)$ multiplied by renormalization scale dependent Wilson coefficients $C_i(\mu)$ that act as coupling constants:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{EFT}} = \sum_i C_i(\mu) O_i(x). \quad (3.1)$$

The Wilson coefficients will then depend on the large energy scale Λ_{high} while the operators themselves only depend on the much lower scale Λ_{low} . Higher dimensional operators are power suppressed in the expansion parameter $\lambda = \Lambda_{\text{low}}/\Lambda_{\text{high}}$ and one can calculate all needed Wilson coefficients order by order in a matching procedure.

Even though often times the method of regions is a sufficient tool to deal with multiscale problems, EFTs cannot only be used to reproduce the same results, but give rise to factorization and resummation methods that are very efficient in dealing with Sudakov logarithms of the form $\alpha_r^n \ln^{2n-k} \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{high}}}{\Lambda_{\text{low}}} \right)$ that arise in all orders of perturbation theory.

3.2 Scalar SCET

To reproduce the integrals from the previous section (Eqs. (2.30) to (2.33)), we begin by writing down the ϕ^3 Lagrangian density:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi) = \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \phi(x) \partial^\mu \phi(x) - \frac{g}{3!} \phi^3(x). \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.1: All possible interaction vertices produced by the scalar SCET Lagrangian density. Dashed lines correspond to c -particles, dotted lines correspond to \bar{c} -particles and jagged lines correspond to soft particles.

Splitting the field $\phi(x) = \phi_c(x) + \phi_{\bar{c}}(x) + \phi_s(x)$ – where the derivatives of $\phi_{c,\bar{c}}(x)$ and $\phi_s(x)$ scale as the collinear and soft momenta respectively and the power counting is the same as in Eq. (2.26) – and keeping only terms that obey momentum conservation, we arrive at:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi) = \mathcal{L}(\phi_c) + \mathcal{L}(\phi_{\bar{c}}) + \mathcal{L}(\phi_s) - \frac{g}{2}\phi_c^2(x)\phi_s(x) - \frac{g}{2}\phi_{\bar{c}}^2(x)\phi_s(x). \quad (3.3)$$

Because of the differently scaling components, the soft field is almost constant for different values of x_{\perp} or x_{\pm} when combined with ϕ_c (or x_{-} when combined with $\phi_{\bar{c}}$). It is therefore possible to substitute

$$\phi_c^2(x)\phi_s(x) \rightarrow \phi_c^2(x)\phi_s(x_{-}), \quad (3.4)$$

$$\phi_{\bar{c}}^2(x)\phi_s(x) \rightarrow \phi_{\bar{c}}^2(x)\phi_s(x_{+}). \quad (3.5)$$

In order to arrive at the Sudakov form factor, we have to introduce an external current operator J , made up of these scalar fields, that corresponds to the electro-magnetic current in collider processes and produces collinear (c and \bar{c}) particles. The most general form then involves terms like $\phi_c^n(x)\phi_{\bar{c}}^m(x)$ as well as derivatives of the fields $\partial^\mu\phi_c(x)$, $n \cdot \partial\phi_{\bar{c}}(x)$, etc.. Using the fact that only derivatives along directions of large energy flow are not power suppressed in λ , we can combine all these terms in a Taylor series of non-local field operators:

$$\phi_c(x + s\bar{n}) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{s^i}{i!} (\bar{n} \cdot \partial)^i \phi_c(x), \quad (3.6)$$

$$\phi_{\bar{c}}(x + tn) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^i}{i!} (n \cdot \partial)^i \phi_{\bar{c}}(x). \quad (3.7)$$

While it turns out that the Wilson coefficients of interaction terms in the Lagrangian are just equal to one, the current operator

$$\begin{aligned}
 J &= J_2 + J_3 + \dots \\
 &= \int ds dt C_2(t, s, \mu) \phi_c(x + s\bar{n}) \phi_{\bar{c}}(x + tn) \\
 &\quad + \int ds dt_1 dt_2 C_3(t_1, t_2, s, \mu) \phi_c(x + s\bar{n}) \phi_{\bar{c}}(x + t_1 n) \phi_{\bar{c}}(x + t_2 n) + (c \leftrightarrow \bar{c}) \\
 &\quad + \dots \\
 &= \text{[Feynman diagrams]} + \dots \quad (3.8)
 \end{aligned}$$

contains multiple Wilson coefficients that have to be calculated order by order in a matching procedure.

3.2.1 Matching of Wilson coefficients

Figure 3.2: Calculating the Wilson coefficients by matching full and effective theory together.

The Fourier transform of Wilson coefficients can be expanded in powers of the coupling constant

$$\tilde{C}_2 = \tilde{C}_2^{(0)} + g^2 \tilde{C}_2^{(1)} + g^4 \tilde{C}_2^{(2)} + \mathcal{O}(g^6), \quad (3.9)$$

$$\tilde{C}_3 = g \tilde{C}_3^{(0)} + g^3 \tilde{C}_3^{(1)} + g^5 \tilde{C}_3^{(2)} + \mathcal{O}(g^7) \quad (3.10)$$

and the results of both full and effective theory Feynman diagrams can be compared, as shown in

3.2. Scalar SCET

Figure 3.2. One finds that the Wilson coefficients up to $\mathcal{O}(g^1)$ are:

$$\tilde{C}_2 = 1 + \mathcal{O}(g^2), \quad (3.11)$$

$$\tilde{C}_3 = \frac{g}{-(\bar{n} \cdot p)(n \cdot l_2) + i0} + \mathcal{O}(g^3). \quad (3.12)$$

Returning now to the scalar Sudakov form factor, we can write down all four scalar SCET diagrams

Figure 3.3: Four diagrams describing the Sudakov form factor in both the full theory as well as SCET.

contributing up to $\mathcal{O}(g^2)$ (Figure 3.3) by using the values for the Wilson coefficients from above. These SCET diagrams actually have a one to one correspondence to the integrals of the previous chapter (Eqs. (2.30) to (2.33)). This can be illustrated by taking a closer look at one of the diagrams:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times \tilde{C}_3^{(0)} = i\pi^{-\frac{d}{2}} \tilde{\mu}^{2\epsilon} \int d^d k \frac{1}{(k^2 + i0) [(k+l)^2 + i0]} \times \underbrace{\frac{1}{-(\bar{n} \cdot p) [n \cdot (-k)] + i0}}_{\tilde{C}_3^{(0)}} \\
 & = i\pi^{-\frac{d}{2}} \tilde{\mu}^{2\epsilon} \int d^d k \frac{1}{(k^2 + i0) [(k+l)^2 + i0] [2p_- \cdot k_+ + i0]} \\
 & = I_{\bar{c}}. \quad (3.13)
 \end{aligned}$$

It should be noted that in Figure 3.2 as well as Figure 3.3 the right-hand side always contains diagrams in which the hard propagators, that are able to produce a $c\bar{c}$ -pair, have been collapsed to a point and their scaling has been absorbed into the Wilson coefficients.

3.3 QCD SCET

In QCD, we are dealing with fields that are not scalars but have multiple components which scale differently with regard to λ . So additionally to splitting the fields as previously

$$A^\mu(x) \rightarrow A_s^\mu(x) + A_c^\mu(x) + A_{\bar{c}}^\mu(x), \quad (3.14)$$

$$\psi(x) \rightarrow \psi_s(x) + \psi_c(x) + \psi_{\bar{c}}(x), \quad (3.15)$$

we have to split each collinear component further into

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_c(x) &= \frac{\not{n}\not{\bar{n}}}{4}\psi_c + \frac{\not{\bar{n}}\not{n}}{4}\psi_c & \psi_{\bar{c}}(x) &= \frac{\not{\bar{n}}\not{n}}{4}\psi_{\bar{c}} + \frac{\not{n}\not{\bar{n}}}{4}\psi_{\bar{c}} \\ &\equiv \zeta_c(x) + \eta_c(x), & &\equiv \zeta_{\bar{c}}(x) + \eta_{\bar{c}}(x) \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

and

$$A_c^\mu(x) = (n \cdot A_c(x)) \frac{\bar{n}^\mu}{2} + (\bar{n} \cdot A_c(x)) \frac{n^\mu}{2} + A_{c,\perp}(x), \quad (3.17)$$

$$A_{\bar{c}}^\mu(x) = (n \cdot A_{\bar{c}}(x)) \frac{\bar{n}^\mu}{2} + (\bar{n} \cdot A_{\bar{c}}(x)) \frac{n^\mu}{2} + A_{\bar{c},\perp}(x). \quad (3.18)$$

In order to quantify the scaling of each component, we can look at the two-point correlation functions:

$$\langle 0 | T \{ \zeta_c(x) \bar{\zeta}_c(0) \} | 0 \rangle = \int \frac{d^4 p}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{i}{p^2 + i0} e^{-ip \cdot x} \frac{\not{n}\not{\bar{n}}}{4} \not{p} \frac{\not{\bar{n}}\not{n}}{4} \sim \lambda^4 \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \lambda^0 = \lambda^2, \quad (3.19)$$

$$\langle 0 | T \{ \zeta_{\bar{c}}(x) \bar{\zeta}_{\bar{c}}(0) \} | 0 \rangle = \int \frac{d^4 p}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{i}{p^2 + i0} e^{-ip \cdot x} \frac{\not{\bar{n}}\not{n}}{4} \not{p} \frac{\not{n}\not{\bar{n}}}{4} \sim \lambda^4 \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \lambda^0 = \lambda^2, \quad (3.20)$$

$$\langle 0 | T \{ \eta_c(x) \bar{\eta}_c(0) \} | 0 \rangle = \int \frac{d^4 p}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{i}{p^2 + i0} e^{-ip \cdot x} \frac{\not{n}\not{\bar{n}}}{4} \not{p} \frac{\not{\bar{n}}\not{n}}{4} \sim \lambda^4 \lambda^2 \frac{1}{\lambda^2} = \lambda^4, \quad (3.21)$$

$$\langle 0 | T \{ \eta_{\bar{c}}(x) \bar{\eta}_{\bar{c}}(0) \} | 0 \rangle = \int \frac{d^4 p}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{i}{p^2 + i0} e^{-ip \cdot x} \frac{\not{\bar{n}}\not{n}}{4} \not{p} \frac{\not{n}\not{\bar{n}}}{4} \sim \lambda^4 \lambda^2 \frac{1}{\lambda^2} = \lambda^4, \quad (3.22)$$

$$\langle 0 | T \{ \psi_s(x) \bar{\psi}_s(0) \} | 0 \rangle = \int \frac{d^4 p}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{i \not{p}}{p^2 + i0} e^{-ip \cdot x} \sim (\lambda^2)^4 \lambda^2 \frac{1}{\lambda^4} = \lambda^6, \quad (3.23)$$

$$\langle 0 | T \{ A^\mu(x) A^\nu(0) \} | 0 \rangle = \int \frac{d^4 p}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{i}{p^2 + i0} e^{-ip \cdot x} \left[-g^{\mu\nu} + \xi \frac{p^\mu p^\nu}{p^2} \right] \sim p^\mu p^\nu. \quad (3.24)$$

We have so far set the mass m of the quarks to zero and we will discuss how to work with massive quarks at a later point. Let us now summarize the different scalings of all components:

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{c/\bar{c}} &\sim \lambda, & \eta_{c/\bar{c}} &\sim \lambda^2, & \psi_s &\sim \lambda^3, \\ A_c &\sim (\lambda^2, 1, \lambda), & A_{\bar{c}} &\sim (1, \lambda^2, \lambda), & A_s &\sim (\lambda^2, \lambda^2, \lambda^2). \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

Because the QCD Lagrangian is quadratic in the quark field components $\zeta_{c/\bar{c}}$ and $\eta_{c/\bar{c}}$, it is possible to integrate one of them out completely in the path integral formalism (see Ref. [19]). An obvious choice is of course to remove the $\eta_{c/\bar{c}}$ components, since they are of a higher order in λ compared to $\zeta_{c/\bar{c}}$ and

thus do not describe processes we are interested in.

Most interaction terms, generated by inserting the field operators from Eqs. (3.14) and (3.15) into the QCD Lagrangian density, are power suppressed in λ . Soft-collinear interactions, that involve either soft quark fields ψ_s or components of A_s^μ that are power suppressed compared to the same component of the collinear field $A_{c/\bar{c}}^\mu$, can thus be neglected. This results in the following SCET Lagrangian density:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{SCET}} = & \bar{\psi}_s(x) i \not{D}_s \psi_s(x) - \frac{1}{4} \left(G_{\mu\nu}^{A,s} \right)^2 \\ & + \left[\bar{\zeta}_c(x) \frac{\not{n}}{2} \left(in \cdot D + i \not{D}_{c,\perp} \frac{1}{i \not{n} \cdot D_c} i \not{D}_{c,\perp} \right) \zeta_c(x) - \frac{1}{4} \left(G_{\mu\nu}^{A,c} \right)^2 + (n \leftrightarrow \bar{n}) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

with

$$iD_\mu^s \equiv i\partial_\mu + gA_\mu^{A,s}(x)T^A, \quad (3.27)$$

$$iD_\mu^c \equiv i\partial_\mu + gA_\mu^{A,c}(x)T^A, \quad (3.28)$$

$$in \cdot D \equiv in \cdot \partial + gn \cdot A_c(x) + gn \cdot A_s(x_-), \quad (3.29)$$

$$D^\mu \equiv n \cdot D \frac{\bar{n}^\mu}{2} + \bar{n} \cdot D_c \frac{n^\mu}{2} + D_{c,\perp}^\mu, \quad (3.30)$$

$$G_{\mu\nu}^s = \frac{i}{g} [D_\mu^s, D_\nu^s], \quad (3.31)$$

$$G_{\mu\nu}^c = \frac{i}{g} [D_\mu^c, D_\nu^c]. \quad (3.32)$$

3.3.1 Gauge Transformations and Wilson Lines

In the same way as QCD, we want our SCET Lagrangian density to be invariant under local gauge transformations of the same form as in Eq. (2.5). Because we now have soft and collinear fields, we also have to introduce two different gauge transformations

$$V_s(x) = (\mathbf{1} + i\kappa_s^A(x)T^A), \quad \text{with } \partial\kappa_s \sim \lambda^2\kappa_s \quad (3.33)$$

and

$$V_{c/\bar{c}}(x) = (\mathbf{1} + i\kappa_{c/\bar{c}}^A(x)T^A), \quad \text{with } \partial\kappa_{c/\bar{c}} \sim \begin{cases} (\lambda^2, 1, \lambda)\kappa_c \\ (1, \lambda^2, \lambda)\kappa_{\bar{c}} \end{cases}. \quad (3.34)$$

Up to leading order in λ , the fields transform in the following way:

Soft transformation

$$\psi_s(x) \rightarrow V_s(x)\psi_s(x), \quad (3.35)$$

$$A_s^\mu(x) \rightarrow V_s(x)A_s^\mu(x)V_s^\dagger(x) + \frac{i}{g}V_s(x) \left[\partial^\mu, V_s^\dagger(x) \right], \quad (3.36)$$

$$\zeta_{c/\bar{c}}(x) \rightarrow V_s(x_{-/++})\zeta_{c/\bar{c}}, \quad (3.37)$$

$$A_{c/\bar{c}}^\mu(x) \rightarrow V_s(x_{-/++})A_{c/\bar{c}}^\mu(x)V_s^\dagger(x_{-/++}). \quad (3.38)$$

Collinear transformations

$$\psi_s(x) \rightarrow \psi_s(x), \quad (3.39)$$

$$A_s^\mu(x) \rightarrow A_s^\mu(x), \quad (3.40)$$

$$\zeta_{c/\bar{c}} \rightarrow V_{c/\bar{c}}(x)\zeta_{c/\bar{c}}, \quad (3.41)$$

$$A_c^\mu(x) \rightarrow V_c(x)A_c^\mu(x)V_c^\dagger(x) + \frac{1}{g}V_c(x) \left[i\partial^\mu + g\frac{\bar{n}^\mu}{2}n \cdot A_s(x_-), V_c^\dagger(x) \right], \quad (3.42)$$

$$A_{\bar{c}}^\mu(x) \rightarrow V_{\bar{c}}(x)A_{\bar{c}}^\mu(x)V_{\bar{c}}^\dagger(x) + \frac{1}{g}V_{\bar{c}}(x) \left[i\partial^\mu + g\frac{n^\mu}{2}\bar{n} \cdot A_s(x_+), V_{\bar{c}}^\dagger(x) \right], \quad (3.43)$$

In order to build gauge invariant blocks out of non-local operators (similar to Eqs. (3.6) and (3.7)), we also have to introduce so called Wilson lines,

$$\mathcal{W}_c(x) = P \exp \left[ig \int_{-\infty}^0 ds \bar{n} \cdot A_c(x + s\bar{n}) \right], \quad (3.44)$$

$$\mathcal{W}_{\bar{c}}(x) = P \exp \left[ig \int_{-\infty}^0 ds n \cdot A_{\bar{c}}(x + sn) \right], \quad (3.45)$$

$$\mathcal{Y}_n(x) = P \exp \left[ig \int_{-\infty}^0 ds n \cdot A_s(x + sn) \right], \quad (3.46)$$

that have to be combined with the quark fields in the following way:

$$\chi_c(x) \equiv \mathcal{W}_c^\dagger \zeta_c(x), \quad \chi_{\bar{c}}(x) \equiv \mathcal{W}_{\bar{c}}^\dagger \zeta_{\bar{c}}(x). \quad (3.47)$$

3.3.2 Decoupling Transformation

While the collinear Wilson lines can be used to preserve gauge symmetry, soft Wilson lines are useful to decouple collinear fields from soft fields in the leading order Lagrangian density. This can be achieved by redefining the collinear fields,

$$\zeta_c(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}_n(x_-)\zeta_c^{(0)}(x), \quad \zeta_{\bar{c}}(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}_{\bar{n}}(x_+)\zeta_{\bar{c}}^{(0)}(x), \quad (3.48)$$

$$A_c^\mu(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}_n(x_-)A_c^{(0)\mu}(x)\mathcal{Y}_n^\dagger(x_-), \quad A_{\bar{c}}^\mu(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}_{\bar{n}}(x_+)A_{\bar{c}}^{(0)\mu}(x)\mathcal{Y}_{\bar{n}}^\dagger(x_+), \quad (3.49)$$

and thus removing any interaction term between the soft gluon field and collinear quark or gluon fields at leading power in λ .

Let us now turn to the electro-magnetic quark current operator $J^\mu = \sum_q e_q \bar{\psi}_q \gamma^\mu \psi_q$. Similarly to the scalar current in Eq. (3.8), we can write J^μ as a product of non-local field operators and Wilson coefficients:

$$J^\mu(x) = \int ds \int dt C_V(s, t) \bar{\chi}_c(x + s\bar{n}) \gamma^\mu \chi_{\bar{c}}(x + tn). \quad (3.50)$$

Applying the decoupling transformation and exploiting the fact that $\not{n}\chi_c = \not{\bar{n}}\chi_{\bar{c}} = 0$ yields:

$$J^\mu(x) = \int ds \int dt C_V(s, t) \bar{\chi}_c^{(0)}(x + s\bar{n}) \mathcal{Y}_n^\dagger(0) \mathcal{Y}_{\bar{n}}(0) \gamma_\perp^\mu \chi_{\bar{c}}^{(0)}(x + tn), \quad (3.51)$$

where the current operator has factorized into four different pieces, namely the Wilson coefficients C_V , the collinear and anti-collinear building blocks $\bar{\chi}_c$ and $\chi_{\bar{c}}$ and the soft Wilson lines \mathcal{Y}_n , which each depend only on their respective scaling. Additionally, all interactions between soft gluons fields and collinear quark or gluon fields have been removed from the leading order Lagrangian.

The cross section for $t\bar{t}$ -production $\sigma_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}+X}$ can then be factorized (see [3]) in the form of a convolution:

$$d\sigma_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}+X} = B_n \otimes B_{\bar{n}} \otimes \text{Tr} \{H \otimes S\}, \quad (3.52)$$

with a hard function H that contains all information of the Wilson coefficients, which depend on the scale Q^2 , while the two beam functions B_i consist of collinear emissions by the beam directions n^μ and \bar{n}^ν . Last but not least, the soft function S depends only on low-energetic emissions by and between the top quark, anti-top quark and the initial state partons. While in general there would also be jet functions describing the emission of collinear particles by the final state partons, they have been regularized by the mass of the top and anti-top quark. Because of the colour charged quarks in the final state, both H and S are matrices in colour space.

Next-to-Next-to Leading Order Real-Virtual Corrections to Soft Functions

4.1 General Form of a Dijet Partonic Soft Function

For the sake of solving RGEs, it is convenient to change the convolution in Eq. (3.52) into a simple multiplication. As long as the convoluted functions are only differential in a single variable, this can be achieved by a Laplace transform:

$$h(\omega) = \int_0^\infty d\omega_1 \int_0^\infty d\omega_2 \delta(\omega - \omega_1 - \omega_2) f(\omega_1) g(\omega_2) \quad (4.1)$$

$$\longrightarrow \tilde{h}(\tau) = \int_0^\infty d\omega e^{-\omega\tau} h(\omega) = \underbrace{\int_0^\infty d\omega_1 e^{-\omega_1\tau} f(\omega_1)}_{\tilde{f}(\tau)} \underbrace{\int_0^\infty d\omega_2 e^{-\omega_2\tau} g(\omega_2)}_{\tilde{g}(\tau)}. \quad (4.2)$$

After the Laplace transform from above, we end up with a soft function that looks like:

$$\tilde{S}(\tau, \mu) = \sum_{X_s} \mathcal{M}(\tau; \{k_i\}) \langle 0 | \mathcal{Y}_n^\dagger(0) \mathcal{Y}_{\bar{n}}(0) \mathcal{Y}_v^\dagger(0) \mathcal{Y}_{\bar{v}}(0) | X_s \rangle \langle X_s | \mathcal{Y}_{\bar{v}}^\dagger(0) \mathcal{Y}_v(0) \mathcal{Y}_n^\dagger(0) \mathcal{Y}_{\bar{n}}(0) | 0 \rangle. \quad (4.3)$$

Here $\mathcal{M}(\tau; \{k_i\})$ is an exponential measurement function of the soft emission momenta k_i ,

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau; \{k_i\}) = \exp[-\tau\omega(\{k_i\})], \quad (4.4)$$

with $\omega(\{k_i\})$ originating from a kinematic δ -function similar to the one in Eq. (4.1), and thus being dependent on the specific observable. We have also switched from only two collinear directions n^μ and \bar{n}^μ to four directions including the reference vectors

$$v^\mu = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}, 0, \frac{\beta \sin \vartheta}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}, \frac{\beta \cos \vartheta}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} \right), \quad (4.5)$$

and

$$\bar{v}^\mu = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}, 0, -\frac{\beta \sin \vartheta}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}, -\frac{\beta \cos \vartheta}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} \right). \quad (4.6)$$

These reference vectors are back-to-back in the centre of mass frame and describe massive quarks with velocity β . Calculating the scalar products of the reference vectors with each other and with the two light-like directions yields:

$$v^2 = \bar{v}^2 = 1, \quad (4.7)$$

$$v \cdot \bar{v} = \bar{v} \cdot v = \frac{1 + \beta^2}{1 - \beta^2}, \quad (4.8)$$

$$v \cdot \bar{n} = \bar{v} \cdot n = \frac{1 + \beta \cos \vartheta}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}, \quad (4.9)$$

$$v \cdot n = \bar{v} \cdot \bar{n} = \frac{1 - \beta \cos \vartheta}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}. \quad (4.10)$$

4.1.1 Measurement Functions

There are several useful assumptions regarding the angular and $n \leftrightarrow \bar{n}$ symmetries as well as mass dimension of $\omega(\{k_i\})$ (details can be found in Ref. [20]), that leave us with the following general ansatz for a one-emission measurement function:

$$\mathcal{M}_1(\tau, k) = \exp \left[-\tau k_T \left(y_k^{n/2} f_A(y_k, t_k) \theta(1 - y_k) + y_k^{-n/2} f_B(y_k^{-1}, t_k) \theta(y_k - 1) \right) \right], \quad (4.11)$$

where we have introduced a phase-space parametrisation of the form

$$y_k = \frac{k_+}{k_-}, \quad k_T = \sqrt{k_+ k_-}, \quad t_k = \frac{1 - \cos \theta_k}{2}. \quad (4.12)$$

The two limits of the rapidity $y_k \rightarrow 0$ and $y_k \rightarrow \infty$ correspond to collinear divergences and the limit of the transverse momentum $k_T \rightarrow 0$ corresponds to the soft divergence. An arbitrary reference vector ℓ^μ specifies the azimuthal angular dependence $\theta_k = \angle(\vec{\ell}_\perp, \vec{k}_{i,\perp})$.

Let us now determine the values of n and $f_{A/B}$ for the two observables we will consider in the next sections. We start with the **zero-jettiness** variable (see Ref. [21]) which is used as a measure of how much the – in this case soft – hadronic, final state particles are aligned to the beam direction:

$$\omega_{0\text{-jet.}}(k) = \min(k_+, k_-) = \min \left(k_T \sqrt{y_k}, \frac{k_T}{\sqrt{y_k}} \right) = \begin{cases} k_T y_k^{1/2}, & 0 \leq y_k \leq 1. \\ k_T y_k^{-1/2}, & 1 \leq y_k \leq \infty. \end{cases} \quad (4.13)$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad n = 1, \quad f_A(y_k, t_k) = 1, \quad f_B(y_k^{-1}, t_k) = f_B(y_k, t_k) = 1. \quad (4.14)$$

The second observable we will be using in our calculation is represented by the **threshold-resummation** variable. It corresponds to a kinematic region in which the QCD radiation is purely soft and there is a restriction on the emitted energy $2k^0 = k_+ + k_-$:

$$\omega_{\text{TR}}(k) = k_+ + k_- = k_T \left(\sqrt{y_k} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{y_k}} \right) = k_T y_k^{-1/2} (1 + y_k). \quad (4.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \quad n = -1, \quad f_A(y_k, t_k) &= (1 + y_k), & f_B(y_k^{-1}, t_k) &= \frac{1 + y_k}{y_k}, \\ & & \Rightarrow \quad f_B(y_k, t_k) &= (1 + y_k). \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

4.1.2 Next-to Leading Order Soft Function

We can now expand the soft function from Eq. (4.3) in a perturbative series:

$$\tilde{S}(\tau, \mu) = 1 + \left(\frac{Z_\alpha \alpha_r}{4\pi} \right) (\mu^2 \bar{\tau}^2)^\varepsilon \tilde{S}^{(1)}(\varepsilon) + \left(\frac{Z_\alpha \alpha_r}{4\pi} \right)^2 (\mu^2 \bar{\tau}^2)^{2\varepsilon} \tilde{S}^{(2)}(\varepsilon) + \dots, \quad (4.17)$$

with

$$\tilde{S}^{(1)}(\varepsilon) = \sum_{i,j} \mathcal{T}_i^A \mathcal{T}_j^A \mathcal{S}_{ij}^{(1)}(\varepsilon), \quad (4.18)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{ij}^{(1)}(\varepsilon) = -\tau^{-2\varepsilon} \int \frac{d^d k}{(2\pi)^d} \delta(k^2) \theta(k^0) \mathcal{M}_1(\tau, k) \left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(1)}(k) \right|^2. \quad (4.19)$$

The indices $i, j \in \{n, \bar{n}, v, \bar{v}\}$ in the matrix element $\mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(1)}(k)$ describe the correlation of both parton i and parton j emitting a soft gluon. Furthermore, $\bar{\tau} = \tau e^{\gamma_E}$ and the colour-charge operator \mathcal{T}_i^A (see Ref. [22]) has been introduced:

$$\mathcal{T}_{CB}^A \equiv i f^{ABC}, \quad \text{if the emitting parton is a gluon,} \quad (4.20)$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{ab}^A \equiv T_{ab}^A, \quad \text{if the emitting parton is a quark,} \quad (4.21)$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{ab}^A \equiv -T_{ab}^A, \quad \text{if the emitting parton is an antiquark.} \quad (4.22)$$

The product $\delta(k^2)\theta(k^0)$ in the integrand of Eq. (4.19) excludes all negative values for both k_+ and k_- , as can be seen in Fig. 4.1. We will now use the phase-space parametrisation in Eq. (4.12) to rewrite the integral measure in terms of these new variables. To do this, we will first change to light-cone coordinates, evaluate the angular integrals of the $(d-2)$ -dimensional vector k_\perp^μ ,

$$\int d^{d-2} k_\perp = \int d|\vec{k}_\perp| |\vec{k}_\perp|^{1-2\varepsilon} \int d(\cos \theta_k) \sin^{-1-2\varepsilon}(\theta_k) \underbrace{\int d\Omega_{d-3}}_{\frac{2\pi^{\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon}}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon)}}, \quad (4.23)$$

and we are left with:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S}_{ij}^{(1)} &= -\frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon} \tau^{-2\varepsilon}}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon) (2\pi)^d} \int_0^\infty dk_+ \int_0^\infty dk_- \int_0^\infty d|\vec{k}_\perp| \delta(k_+ k_- - |\vec{k}_\perp|) |\vec{k}_\perp|^{1-2\varepsilon} \\ &\quad \times \int d(\cos \theta_k) \sin^{-1-2\varepsilon}(\theta_k) \mathcal{M}_1(\tau, k) \left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(1)}(k) \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.24)$$

Figure 4.1: The delta function (red) and the Heaviside function (blue) confine the integration region for k_+ and k_- to the top right quadrant.

Next we can perform the integration over $|\vec{k}_\perp|$ and switch to the final parametrisation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{S}_{ij}^{(1)} &= -\frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon} \tau^{-2\varepsilon}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon\right) (2\pi)^d} \int_0^\infty \frac{dy_k}{y_k} \int_0^1 \frac{dt_k}{[4t_k(1-t_k)]^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}} \\
 &\quad \times \int_0^\infty dk_T (k_T)^{1-2\varepsilon} \mathcal{M}_1(\tau, k) \left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(1)}(k) \right|^2 \Big|_{|\vec{k}_\perp|=k_T}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.25}$$

Since the measurement function is exponential in k_T and the NLO matrix element is proportional to $(k_T)^{-2}$, the integral over k_T is of the form:

$$\int_0^\infty dx' (x')^{A-1} \exp(-Bx') = B^{-A} \Gamma(A), \tag{4.26}$$

with

$$A = -2\varepsilon, \quad B = \tau \left[y_k^{n/2} f_A(y_k, t_k) \theta(1-y_k) + y_k^{-n/2} f_B(y_k^{-1}, t_k) \theta(y_k-1) \right]. \tag{4.27}$$

With only the integrals over y_k and t_k left, we arrive at:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{S}_{ij}^{(1)} &= -\frac{32\pi^3 \pi^{\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon} \Gamma(-2\varepsilon) (4\pi e^{\gamma_E})^{-\varepsilon}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon\right) (2\pi)^d} \int_0^\infty \frac{dy_k}{y_k} \int_0^1 \frac{dt_k}{[4t_k(1-t_k)]^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}} \mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(1)}(y_k, t_k) \\
 &\quad \times \left[y_k^{n/2} f_A(y_k, t_k) \theta(1-y_k) + y_k^{-n/2} f_B(y_k^{-1}, t_k) \theta(y_k-1) \right]^{2\varepsilon}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.28}$$

Here $\mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(1)}$ is the NLO k_T -stripped matrix element:

$$\mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(1)}(y_k, t_k) \equiv \frac{k_T^2 \left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(1)}(k) \right|^2}{32\pi^3 (4\pi e^{\gamma_E})^{-\varepsilon}} \Big|_{|\vec{k}_\perp|=k_T} = k_T^2 \frac{v_i \cdot v_j}{(v_i \cdot k)(v_j \cdot k)} \Big|_{|\vec{k}_\perp|=k_T}, \quad v_i, v_j \in \{n, \bar{n}, v, \bar{v}\}. \quad (4.29)$$

Let us now turn to the scalar products $v \cdot k$ and $\bar{v} \cdot k$ that are still missing. We can immediately evaluate them at $|\vec{k}_\perp| = k_T$ and then extract the k_T dependence:

$$\begin{aligned} v \cdot k \Big|_{|\vec{k}_\perp|=k_T} &= k_T \left[\frac{1 - \beta \cos \vartheta}{2\sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \sqrt{y_k}} + \frac{(1 + \beta \cos \vartheta) \sqrt{y_k}}{2\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} - |\vec{v}_\perp| \cos \theta_k \right] \\ &= k_T \left[\frac{(1 - \beta \cos \vartheta) \frac{1}{\sqrt{y_k}} + (1 + \beta \cos \vartheta) \sqrt{y_k}}{2\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} - \frac{\beta \sin \vartheta}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \cos \theta_k \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4.30)$$

$$\bar{v} \cdot k \Big|_{|\vec{k}_\perp|=k_T} = k_T \left[\frac{(1 + \beta \cos \vartheta) \frac{1}{\sqrt{y_k}} + (1 - \beta \cos \vartheta) \sqrt{y_k}}{2\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} + \frac{\beta \sin \vartheta}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \cos \theta_k \right], \quad (4.31)$$

where we have used the definition of θ_k from section 4.1.1, with $\ell^\mu \rightarrow v^\mu$, and the exact form of v and \bar{v} from Eqs. (4.5) and (4.6). In the final step, we can split the integration over y_k in two parts according to the Heaviside functions and use the integrand's symmetry of $y_k \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{y_k}$ to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S}_{ij}^{(1)} &= -\frac{2e^{-\gamma_E \varepsilon} \Gamma(-2\varepsilon)}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} - \varepsilon\right)} \int_0^1 \frac{dy_k}{y_k^{1-n\varepsilon}} \int_0^1 \frac{dt_k}{[4t_k(1-t_k)]^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}} \left\{ [f_A(y_k, t_k)]^{2\varepsilon} \mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(1)}(y_k, t_k) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + [f_B(y_k, t_k)]^{2\varepsilon} \mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(1)}\left(\frac{1}{y_k}, t_k\right) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.32)$$

As previously mentioned, the soft divergence was incorporated in the integral over k_T and has now been absorbed into the gamma function $\Gamma(-2\varepsilon)$. Both collinear divergences now arise in the limit $y_k \rightarrow 0$ and so the integral has to be split into plus-distributions,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \frac{dy_k}{y_k^{1-n\varepsilon}} \mathcal{J}_{ij}(y_k, t_k) f(y_k, t_k)^{2\varepsilon} &= \int_0^1 dy_k \left[\frac{\delta(y_k)}{n\varepsilon} + (y_k)_+^{-1+n\varepsilon} \right] \mathcal{J}_{ij}(y_k, t_k) [f(y_k, t_k)]^{2\varepsilon} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{J}_{ij}(0, t_k) [f(0, t_k)]^{2\varepsilon}}{n\varepsilon} \\ &\quad + \int_0^1 dy_k \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{d^\ell}{d\varepsilon^\ell} (y_k)^{-1+n\varepsilon} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \varepsilon^\ell \left\{ \mathcal{J}_{ij}(y_k, t_k) [f(y_k, t_k)]^{2\varepsilon} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \mathcal{J}_{ij}(0, t_k) [f(0, t_k)]^{2\varepsilon} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.33)$$

if the process contains massless particles.

4.1.3 Next-to-Next-to Leading Order Soft Function

The NNLO soft function contains real-virtual corrections as well as double-real emission contributions and can be written as:

$$\tilde{S}^{(2)}(\varepsilon) = \tilde{S}^{(2, \text{RV})}(\varepsilon) + \tilde{S}^{(2, q\bar{q})}(\varepsilon) + \tilde{S}^{(2, gg)}(\varepsilon). \quad (4.34)$$

We will only focus on the real-virtual piece, which can be further split into a term originating from the real part of the loop integral, which contains two-particle correlations similar to the ones in Eq. (4.18), and a term originating from the imaginary part with three-particle correlations:

$$\tilde{S}^{(2, \text{RV})}(\varepsilon) = C_A \underbrace{\sum_{i \neq j} \mathcal{T}_i^A \mathcal{T}_j^A}_{\tilde{S}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon)} \tilde{S}_{ij}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon) + \sum_{i \neq j \neq \ell} (\lambda_{ij} - \lambda_{ik} - \lambda_{jk}) f_{ABC} \mathcal{T}_i^A \mathcal{T}_j^B \mathcal{T}_\ell^C \tilde{S}_{ij\ell}^{(2, \text{Im})}(\varepsilon). \quad (4.35)$$

Here $\lambda_{AB} = \begin{cases} 1, & A \text{ and } B \text{ are both incoming or outgoing,} \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases}$ and the index k denotes the emitted soft parton. While the three-particle correlations term does give a contribution if there are four or more particles, we will only regard the two-particle correlations in the following sections.

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S}_{ij}^{(2, \text{Re})} &= -\frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon} \tau^{-4\varepsilon}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon\right) (2\pi)^{d-1}} \int_0^\infty \frac{dy_k}{y_k} \int_0^1 \frac{dt_k}{[4t_k(1-t_k)]^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}} \\ &\quad \times \int_0^\infty dk_T (k_T)^{1-2\varepsilon} \mathcal{M}_1(\tau, k) \left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(2)}(k) \right|^2 \Big|_{|\vec{k}_\perp|=k_T}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.36)$$

Since the structure is very similar to the one in the previous section, we can follow along the same lines, with the only difference being the fact that the matrix element is now proportional to $(k_T)^{-2(\varepsilon+1)}$ which results in a different value for A in the k_T integral compared to Eq. (4.27):

$$A = -4\varepsilon, \quad B = \tau \left[y_k^{n/2} f_A(y_k, t_k) \theta(1-y_k) + y_k^{-n/2} f_B(y_k^{-1}, t_k) \theta(y_k-1) \right]. \quad (4.37)$$

As a final result, before plugging in the matrix element, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S}_{ij}^{(2, \text{Re})} &= -\frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon} \Gamma(-4\varepsilon)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}-\varepsilon\right) (2\pi)^{d-1}} \int_0^1 \frac{dy_k}{y_k^{1-2n\varepsilon}} \int_0^1 \frac{dt_k}{[4t_k(1-t_k)]^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}} \\ &\quad \times \left\{ [f_A(y_k, t_k)]^{4\varepsilon} \mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(2)}(y_k, t_k) + [f_B(y_k, t_k)]^{4\varepsilon} \mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(2)}\left(\frac{1}{y_k}, t_k\right) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.38)$$

As before, this integral has to be split into plus-distributions (see Eq. (4.33)), if there is at least one massless particle involved.

Figure 4.2: Four possible types of NNLO real-virtual diagrams, including a three gluon vertex *a*), gluon self energy *b*) and external leg emissions *c*) and *d*).

4.2 Real-Virtual Soft Matrix Elements

There are four different types of cut-diagrams (see Figure 4.2), that contribute to the real-virtual correction of the soft function. Because we have four collinear directions, many different versions of each type have to be considered. They can however all be divided into diagrams that involve purely massless (only n^μ and \bar{n}^μ), purely massive (only v^μ and \bar{v}^μ) or both massive and massless (n^μ , \bar{n}^μ , v^μ and \bar{v}^μ) partons.

4.2.1 Massless-Massless

Let us first consider the Feynman rules for the emission of one or two soft gluons by one of the massless partons moving in the n^μ or \bar{n}^μ direction. The definitions of a soft Wilson line from Eq. (3.46) and the field operator in Eq. (2.3) can be used to obtain:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram: } \bar{n} \text{ line with gluon emission } k, \mu, A \end{array} \\
 = g\mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^A \frac{\bar{n}^\mu}{\bar{n} \cdot k + i0}, \quad (4.39)
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram: } n \text{ line with gluon emission } k, \mu, A \end{array} \\
 = -g\mathcal{T}_n^A \frac{n^\mu}{n \cdot k + i0} \quad (4.40)
 \end{array}$$

and

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram: } \bar{n} \text{ line with two gluon emissions } k_1, \mu, A \text{ and } k_2, \nu, B \end{array} \\
 = g^2 \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^A \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^B \frac{n^\mu n^\nu}{[n \cdot k_1 + i0][n \cdot (k_1 + k_2) + i0]}, \quad (4.41)
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{array}{c} \text{Diagram: } n \text{ line with two gluon emissions } k_2, \nu, B \text{ and } k_1, \mu, A \end{array} \\
 = g^2 \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_n^A \frac{\bar{n}^\nu \bar{n}^\mu}{[\bar{n} \cdot (k_1 + k_2) + i0][\bar{n} \cdot k_1 + i0]}. \quad (4.42)
 \end{array}$$

Most diagrams in the purely massless case result in scaleless integrals and the only non-zero contributions stem from two diagrams of type *a*) in Figure 4.2. The left-hand side of such a diagram is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= -g^3 \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^C f^{ABC} \tilde{\mu}^{3\epsilon} \int \frac{d^d l}{(2\pi)^d} [g^{\mu\nu} (-k - k - l)^\rho + g^{\nu\rho} (k + l + l)^\mu + g^{\rho\mu} (-l + k)^\nu] \\
 &\quad \times \frac{n_\nu}{n \cdot (k + l) + i0} \times \frac{\bar{n}_\rho}{\bar{n} \cdot (-l) + i0} \times \frac{-i}{l^2 + i0} \times \frac{-i}{(k + l)^2 + i0} \times [\varepsilon_\mu^A(k)]^* \\
 &= g^3 \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^C f^{ABC} [\varepsilon_\mu^A(k)]^* \tilde{\mu}^{3\epsilon} \\
 &\quad \times \underbrace{\int \frac{d^d l}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{n^\mu [\bar{n} \cdot (-2k - l)] + (k + 2l)^\mu [\bar{n} \cdot n] + \bar{n}^\mu [n \cdot (-l + k)]}{[n \cdot (k + l) + i0] [\bar{n} \cdot (-l) + i0] [l^2 + i0] [(k + l)^2 + i0]}}_{I^\mu(k)}. \tag{4.43}
 \end{aligned}$$

We can now combine a term *A* in the denominator that is quadratic in *l* with another term *B* that is linear in *l* by introducing a Feynman parameter *x*:

$$\int_0^\infty dx \frac{1}{(A + Bx)^2} = \frac{1}{AB}. \tag{4.44}$$

The result is

$$I_\mu(k) = \int \frac{d^d l}{(2\pi)^d} \int_0^\infty dx \int_0^\infty dy \frac{d^d l}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{n^\mu [\bar{n} \cdot (-2k - l)] + 2(k + 2l)^\mu + \bar{n}^\mu [n \cdot (k - l)]}{[l^2 + x[n \cdot (k + l)] + i0]^2 [(k + l)^2 + y[\bar{n} \cdot (-l)] + i0]^2}. \tag{4.45}$$

In order to bring the denominator in a form that lets us complete the square, it is necessary to introduce one final Feynman parameter *z*:

$$6 \int_0^1 dz \frac{z(1 - z)}{[zA + (1 - z)B]^4} = \frac{1}{A^2 B^2}. \tag{4.46}$$

Using the fact that $k^2 = n^2 = \bar{n}^2 = 0$ we arrive at:

$$I_\mu(k) = 6 \int_0^\infty dx \int_0^\infty dy \int_0^1 dz (1-z) \quad (4.47)$$

$$\times \int \frac{d^d l}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{2(k+2l)^\mu - n^\mu [\bar{n} \cdot (2k+l)] + \bar{n}^\mu [n \cdot (k-l)]}{\left[\left(l + \frac{xzn+2(1-z)k-(1-z)y\bar{n}}{2} \right)^2 - \underbrace{(-xz^2k_+ - xyz(1-z) - y(1-z)^2k_- - i0)}_{\Delta} \right]^4}.$$

We will now shift the integration variable by a finite amount,

$$l^\mu \rightarrow \tilde{l}^\mu - xz \frac{n^\mu}{2} + y(1-z) \frac{\bar{n}^\mu}{2} - (1-z)k^\mu, \quad (4.48)$$

and again drop all terms in the numerator that involve k^2 , n^2 or \bar{n}^2 as well as all terms that are linear in the new integration variable \tilde{l}^μ . The latter can be done since it corresponds to an odd integrand that is integrated over all possible values of \tilde{l} . The final result before calculating the loop-integral is:

$$I_\mu(k) = 6 \int_0^\infty dx \int_0^\infty dy \int_0^1 dz (1-z) \quad (4.49)$$

$$\times \int \frac{d^d \tilde{l}}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{2[y(1-z)\bar{n} + 2(z-1)k - xzn]^\mu - n^\mu [-xz + (1+z)k_-] + \bar{n}^\mu [-y(1-z) + (2-z)k_+]}{[\tilde{l}^2 - \Delta]^4}.$$

With the general formula for loop integrals,

$$\int \frac{d^d \tilde{l}}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{1}{[\tilde{l}^2 - \Delta]^b} = i(-1)^{-b} \frac{1}{(4\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}}} \frac{1}{\Delta^{b-\frac{d}{2}}} \frac{\Gamma(b-\frac{d}{2})}{\Gamma(b)}$$

$$\stackrel{\substack{b=4 \\ d=4-2\varepsilon}}{=} \frac{i}{(4\pi)^{2-\varepsilon}} \frac{1}{\Delta^{2+\varepsilon}} \frac{\Gamma(2+\varepsilon)}{\Gamma(4)}, \quad (4.50)$$

at hand, we can go ahead and write:

$$I_\mu(k) = i \frac{6\Gamma(2+\varepsilon)}{(4\pi)^{2-\varepsilon}\Gamma(4)} \int_0^\infty dx \int_0^\infty dy \int_0^1 dz (1-z) \quad (4.51)$$

$$\times \frac{2[y(1-z)\bar{n} + 2(z-1)k - xzn]^\mu - n^\mu [-xz + (1+z)k_-] + \bar{n}^\mu [-y(1-z) + (2-z)k_+]}{\underbrace{\left[-xz^2k_+ - xyz(1-z) - y(1-z)^2k_- - i0 \right]^{2+\varepsilon}}_{e^{-i\pi\varepsilon[xz^2k_+ + xyz(1-z) + y(1-z)^2k_-]^{2+\varepsilon}}}}.$$

After integrating over all three Feynman parameters, we end up with:

$$I_\mu(k) = \frac{ie^{i\pi\varepsilon}\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)^2\Gamma(-\varepsilon)^3k_-^{-1-\varepsilon}k_+^{-1-\varepsilon}(\bar{n}_\mu k_+ - n_\mu k_-)}{(4\pi)^{2-\varepsilon}\Gamma(-2\varepsilon)}. \quad (4.52)$$

Let us now calculate the interference with the Born amplitude:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left(\frac{\alpha_r}{4\pi}\right)^2 (\mu^2 e^{2\gamma_E})^{2\varepsilon} C_A \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^B \left| \mathcal{A}_{12}^{(2)}(k) \right|^2 &= \text{Diagram 1} + \text{Diagram 2} \\
 &= -2 \operatorname{Re} \left[g^3 \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^C f^{ABC} \left[\varepsilon_\mu^A(k) \right]^* \tilde{\mu}^{3\varepsilon} \frac{ie^{i\pi\varepsilon} \Gamma(1+\varepsilon)^2 \Gamma(-\varepsilon)^3 k_-^{-1-\varepsilon} k_+^{-1-\varepsilon} (\bar{n}_\mu k_+ - n_\mu k_-)}{(4\pi)^{2-\varepsilon} \Gamma(-2\varepsilon)} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \times \left(-g \tilde{\mu}^\varepsilon \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^D \frac{\bar{n} \cdot \varepsilon^D(k)}{\bar{n} \cdot k} \right) \right]. \tag{4.53}
 \end{aligned}$$

We can now apply the polarisation sum rule $\varepsilon_\nu^D(k) \left[\varepsilon_\mu^A(k) \right]^* = -g_{\mu\nu} \delta^{AD}$ and then rewrite the product $f^{ABC} \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^C \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^A = f^{ABC} \frac{i}{2} f^{CAB} \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^B = i \frac{C_A}{2} \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^B$ to get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= -4g^4 \tilde{\mu}^{4\varepsilon} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{C_A}{2} \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^B \frac{1}{(k_- k_+)^{1+\varepsilon}} \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)^2 \Gamma(-\varepsilon)^3}{\Gamma(-2\varepsilon)} \frac{e^{i\pi\varepsilon}}{(4\pi)^{2-\varepsilon}} \right] \\
 &= -2g^4 C_A \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^B \tilde{\mu}^{4\varepsilon} \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)^2 \Gamma(-\varepsilon)^3 \cos(\pi\varepsilon)}{\Gamma(-2\varepsilon)} \frac{1}{(4\pi)^{2-\varepsilon} (k_- k_+)^{1+\varepsilon}} \\
 &= -2\alpha_r^2 C_A \mathcal{T}_n^B \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}}^B (\mu^2 e^{\gamma_E})^{2\varepsilon} \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)^2 \Gamma(-\varepsilon)^3 \cos(\pi\varepsilon)}{\Gamma(-2\varepsilon)} \frac{1}{(4\pi)^\varepsilon (k_- k_+)^{1+\varepsilon}}. \tag{4.54}
 \end{aligned}$$

The result is proportional to $(k_T)^{-2(\varepsilon+1)}$ and the colour structure is indeed in the same form as in Eq. (4.35). The calculations for $\left| \mathcal{A}_{21}^{(2)}(k) \right|$, $\left| \mathcal{A}_{11}^{(2)}(k) \right|$ and $\left| \mathcal{A}_{22}^{(2)}(k) \right|$ follow along the same lines and we find:

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{21}^{(2)}(k) \right| = \left| \mathcal{A}_{12}^{(2)}(k) \right|, \tag{4.55}$$

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{11}^{(2)}(k) \right| = \left| \mathcal{A}_{22}^{(2)}(k) \right| = 0, \tag{4.56}$$

which can be summarized in the general form:

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(2)}(k) \right|^2 = -32\pi^2 \frac{\Gamma(1+\varepsilon)^2 \Gamma(-\varepsilon)^3 \cos(\pi\varepsilon)}{\Gamma(-2\varepsilon)} \frac{1}{(4\pi e^{2\gamma_E})^\varepsilon} \left[\frac{n_i \cdot n_j}{2(n_i \cdot k)(n_j \cdot k)} \right]^{1+\varepsilon}, \quad n_i, n_j \in \{n, \bar{n}\}. \tag{4.57}$$

Because the amplitude is symmetric under $i \leftrightarrow j$, we will only need $\tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \operatorname{Re})}(\varepsilon)$ as a building block for our results.

4.2.2 Massive-Massive

The calculations for amplitudes with massive quarks are much more elaborate, and we will be using the results of Ref. [24] for all needed power-coefficients in ε . These results are split into three different

kinematic regions, including two timelike configurations with both v_i and v_j either incoming or outgoing and a spacelike region with v_i outgoing and v_j incoming. The two timelike regions only differ in the part that stems from the imaginary part of the amplitude, which we will disregard anyway. Furthermore, the difference between timelike configurations and spacelike configurations vanishes, if the initial partons are assumed to be massless. For our purposes, it is thus sufficient to write the matrix element as:

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(2)}(k) \right|^2 = -32\pi^2 \left(4\pi e^{3\gamma_E} \right)^{-\varepsilon} \left(\frac{2(v_i \cdot v_j)}{2(v_i \cdot k)2(v_j \cdot k)} \right)^\varepsilon (e_{ij} - e_{ii}) \left[\frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} + \sum_{n=-1}^1 \varepsilon^n R_{ij}^{(n)} \right], \quad (4.58)$$

with

$$R_{ij}^{(-1)} = \ln(v_+) - \frac{v_-}{v} \left(\ln \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right), \quad (4.59)$$

$$R_{ij}^{(0)} = \frac{1}{v} \left[\frac{1}{d_i + d_j} \left((\alpha_i v_+ - \alpha_j v_-) \ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + (\alpha_j v_+ - \alpha_i v_-) \ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) \right. \\ \left. + \left(\ln \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) (v_+ \ln(v_+) - \ln(v)) - \text{Li}_2(x) \right] + \frac{1}{2} \ln^2(v_+) + \zeta_2 \left(\frac{7}{v} - \frac{19}{2} \right), \quad (4.60)$$

$$R_{ij}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{d_i + d_j} \left\{ (1 - (d_i + d_j)) \left[\ln \left(1 - \frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) \ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln \left(1 - \frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + 2 \left(\ln \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) \text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \text{Li}_2 \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) - \text{Li}_2(x) \left(\ln \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) \right] \right. \\ \left. + 2 \left(\text{Li}_3(x) - \text{Li}_3 \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) - \text{Li}_3 \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) + \zeta_3 \right) \right] - 7\zeta_2 \left(\ln \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) \\ \left. + \frac{1}{v} \left[\left((\alpha_j v_+ - \alpha_i v_-) \ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + (\alpha_i v_+ - \alpha_j v_-) \ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) \ln(v_+) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + (\alpha_i - \alpha_j) \left(\ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) - \ln^2 \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) \ln(v) - \left(d_i \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + d_j \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) (\text{Li}_2(x) - 7\zeta_2) \right] \right\} \\ \left. + \frac{1}{v} \left\{ \left[\ln(v_+) \left(\frac{3+v}{4} \ln(v_+) - \ln(v) \right) - \frac{9v_-}{2} \zeta_2 \right] \left(\ln \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - \frac{v_-}{6} \left(\ln^3 \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+} \right) + \ln^3 \left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+} \right) \right) + 2 \text{Li}_3(1-x) + \text{Li}_3(x) - \left[\text{Li}_2(x) + \zeta_2 \left(5 + \frac{19}{2} v \right) \right] \ln(v_+) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + 12\zeta_2 \ln(v) \right\} + \frac{1}{6} \ln^3(v_+) - \left(\frac{7}{3} + \frac{1}{v} \right) \zeta_3, \quad (4.61)$$

as well as

$$e_{ij} \equiv \frac{v_i \cdot v_j}{(v_i \cdot k)(v_j \cdot k)}, \quad \alpha_i \equiv \frac{2(v_j \cdot k)}{2(v_i \cdot v_j)2(v_i \cdot k)}, \quad \alpha_j \equiv \frac{2(v_i \cdot k)}{2(v_i \cdot v_j)2(v_j \cdot k)}, \quad (4.62)$$

$$d_i \equiv 1 - 2\alpha_i, \quad d_j \equiv 1 - 2\alpha_j, \quad v \equiv \sqrt{1 - 4\alpha_i \alpha_j}, \quad (4.63)$$

$$v_\pm \equiv \frac{1 \pm v}{2}, \quad x \equiv \frac{v_-}{v_+}. \quad (4.64)$$

Since the incoming partons are massless, the massive-massive case describes the interaction between two massive, outgoing particles, and we are thus only considering the timelike configuration for now. The scalar products in Eqs. (4.30) and (4.31) are related to each other by changing $\cos \theta_k \rightarrow -\cos \theta_k$ as well

as $\cos \vartheta \rightarrow -\cos \vartheta$. For our calculations, it is hence enough to look at only one of the massive-massive amplitudes:

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{34}^{(2)}(\cos \theta_k, \cos \vartheta, \dots) \right|^2 = \left| \mathcal{A}_{43}^{(2)}(-\cos \theta_k, -\cos \vartheta, \dots) \right|^2. \quad (4.65)$$

Since the integral in Eq. (4.38) is invariant under $t_k \leftrightarrow 1 - t_k$, ($\cos \theta_k \leftrightarrow -\cos \theta_k$), one massive-massive building block, e.g. $S_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\cos \vartheta, \beta)$, is enough to calculate the entire contribution to the two-particle correlations.

Furthermore, we can immediately verify that $\left| \mathcal{A}_{ij}^{(2)}(k) \right|^2$ is again proportional to $(k_T)^{-2(\varepsilon+1)}$ because the only term that depends on k_T is

$$\left(\frac{2(v_i \cdot v_j)}{2(v_i \cdot k)2(v_j \cdot k)} \right)^\varepsilon (e_{ij} - e_{ii}) \sim \left(\frac{1}{k_T^2} \right)^\varepsilon \left(\frac{1}{k_T^2} \right) = \left(\frac{1}{k_T} \right)^{2(\varepsilon+1)}, \quad \forall v_i, v_j \in \{n, \bar{n}, v, \bar{v}\}. \quad (4.66)$$

The massless limit of the amplitude can be found by first setting $\ln\left(\frac{\alpha_i}{v_+}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+}\right) = 0$ and then $\alpha_i = \alpha_j = v_- = x = 0$ as well as $d_i = d_j = v = v_+ = 1$. This does indeed reproduce our result from the last section up to $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

4.2.3 Massive-Massless

The massive-massless case now involves two incoming partons as well as the two massive, outgoing top and anti-top quark. We will therefore need to consider the spacelike region and set $\ln\left(\frac{\alpha_j}{v_+}\right) = 0$ followed by $\alpha_j = v_- = x = 0$ and $v = v_+ = d_j = 1$. Because we set the mass of the incoming particle to zero, we will now get an additional collinear divergence of the form $\frac{1}{\varepsilon}$. This means that we will need another coefficient $R_{ij}^{(2)}$ of the matrix element to determine the soft function up to $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0)$ (see Ref. [25]):

$$\begin{aligned} R_{ij}^{(2)} = & \frac{-2}{R_S} \left\{ -4[(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) - (v_j \cdot k)] \left[\text{Li}_4\left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha_i}\right) + \text{Li}_4(1 - \alpha_i) - \text{Li}_4(\alpha_i) \right] \right. \\ & + \pi^4 \frac{(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) - 213(v_j \cdot k)}{720} \\ & + \ln(\alpha_i) (4[(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) - (v_j \cdot k)] \text{Li}_3(1 - \alpha_i) - 2\zeta_3 [2(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) - (v_j \cdot k)]) \\ & + \pi^2 \frac{-4(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) - (v_j \cdot k)}{12} \ln^4(\alpha_i) + 2 \frac{(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) - (v_j \cdot k)}{3} \ln(1 - \alpha_i) \ln^3(\alpha_i) \\ & \left. + \frac{-(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) + 3(v_j \cdot k)}{12} \ln^4(\alpha_i) - \pi^2 \frac{14}{3} [(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k) - (v_j \cdot k)] \text{Li}_2(1 - \alpha_i) \right\}, \quad (4.67) \end{aligned}$$

with

$$R_S = 4[(v_j \cdot k) - 2(v_i \cdot v_j)(v_i \cdot k)]. \quad (4.68)$$

By using the symmetries of the scalar products in Eqs. (4.9), (4.10), (4.30) and (4.31), we additionally find:

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{31}^{(2)}(y_k, \cos \theta_k, \cos \vartheta, \dots) \right|^2 = \left| \mathcal{A}_{41}^{(2)}(y_k, -\cos \theta_k, -\cos \vartheta, \dots) \right|^2, \quad (4.69)$$

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{32}^{(2)}(y_k, \cos \theta_k, \cos \vartheta, \dots) \right|^2 = \left| \mathcal{A}_{42}^{(2)}(y_k, -\cos \theta_k, -\cos \vartheta, \dots) \right|^2 \quad (4.70)$$

and

$$\left| \mathcal{A}_{31}^{(2)}(y_k, \cos \theta_k, \cos \vartheta, \dots) \right|^2 = \left| \mathcal{A}_{32}^{(2)}\left(\frac{1}{y_k}, \cos \theta_k, -\cos \vartheta, \dots\right) \right|^2. \quad (4.71)$$

It should also be noted that the sum in Eq. (4.35) runs over all $i \neq j$, which means that we will need e.g. $\left| \mathcal{A}_{31}^{(2)} \right|$ as well as $\left| \mathcal{A}_{13}^{(2)} \right|$. However, since $e_{11} \sim n^2 = e_{22} \sim \bar{n}^2 = 0$, we can simply rewrite $(e_{ij} - e_{ii}) \rightarrow (2e_{ij} - e_{ii})$ in Eq. (4.35) and sum only over $(i, j) \in \{(3, 1), (3, 2), (4, 1), (4, 2)\}$.

Additionally to the symmetry of the whole integral in Eq. (4.38) regarding $t_k \leftrightarrow 1 - t_k$, the sum $\mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(2)}(y_k, t_k) + \mathcal{J}_{ij}^{(2)}\left(\frac{1}{y_k}, t_k\right)$ is also invariant under $y_k \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{y_k}$, which means that there is only one massive-massless building block, e.g. $\tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\cos \vartheta, \beta)$, needed to calculate the two-particle correlations. Since the massive-massless case involves four colour charged particles, the three-particle correlations also give a non-zero contribution to the total real-virtual soft function.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Building Blocks

Let us begin the presentation of the results by showcasing the three building blocks $\tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \text{Re})}$, $\tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ and $\tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ for both zero-jettiness and threshold-resummation (see Figures A.1 to A.14 in Appendix A). We will be using these building blocks to calculate all the two-particle correlations in Eq. (4.35) up to $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \cos \vartheta, \beta) \equiv & \frac{\tilde{S}_{-4}(\cos \vartheta, \beta)}{\varepsilon^4} + \frac{\tilde{S}_{-3}(\cos \vartheta, \beta)}{\varepsilon^3} + \frac{\tilde{S}_{-2}(\cos \vartheta, \beta)}{\varepsilon^2} + \frac{\tilde{S}_{-1}(\cos \vartheta, \beta)}{\varepsilon} \\ & + \tilde{S}_0(\cos \vartheta, \beta) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (4.72)$$

Since we are mostly interested in $t\bar{t}$ -production, it makes sense to look at two different physical processes, namely $e^+e^- \rightarrow t\bar{t}$ and $pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}$. For the former, we only need the massive-massive building block $\tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ and the colour structure decomposes again to just the colour constant $C_F = -\mathcal{T}_v \cdot \mathcal{T}_{\bar{v}} = \mathcal{T}_v^2 = \mathcal{T}_{\bar{v}}^2$, while for the latter we will need both the massless-massless and massive-massless building blocks, if we consider the top-antitop-pair at threshold to be a colour-octet (see Ref. [7]), or all of the building blocks for the complete $2 \rightarrow 2$ process. In both hadronic $t\bar{t}$ -production processes the colour structure is more complicated, and the soft function does not even decompose into a scalar in the $2 \rightarrow 2$ case.

4.3.2 $e^+e^- \rightarrow t\bar{t}$

For $t\bar{t}$ -production in electron-positron-collision processes, the soft function does not depend on the scattering angle ϑ and we can set e.g. $\cos\vartheta = 1$ in the following. As previously mentioned, for processes that involve only two massive, colour charged particles, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{S}_{e^+e^- \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \beta) &= C_A \left[\mathcal{T}_v \cdot \mathcal{T}_{\bar{v}} \tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, 1, \beta) + \mathcal{T}_v \cdot \mathcal{T}_{\bar{v}} \tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, -1, \beta) \right] \\ &= -C_A C_F \left[\tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, 1, \beta) + \tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, -1, \beta) \right].\end{aligned}\quad (4.73)$$

In order to check our numerical values for the building block $\tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}$, we can compare our results to the Laplace transformed, NNLO real-virtual soft function $S_{Q\bar{Q}}^{\text{RV}(2)}(x_\beta, \varepsilon)$ from Ref. [6], which can be found as an electronic file, given in terms of harmonic polylogs

$$G[\{w_1, \dots, w_n\}; x_\beta] = (-1)^\sigma \text{HPL}[\{w_1, \dots, w_n\}; x_\beta], \quad (4.74)$$

with σ being the number of w_i equal to $+1$ and $x_\beta = \frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta}$.

These polylogs can be evaluated with the HypExp-package (see Ref. [26]) and the results depicting the β dependence of both $\tilde{S}_{e^+e^- \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \beta)$ as well as the analytical results of Ref. [6] for the threshold resummation variable can be seen in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Power coefficients of $\tilde{S}_{e^+e^- \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ as a function of β for the threshold-resummation observable. Analytical results of Ref. [6] are represented by the solid lines and numerical values produced by our building blocks are depicted as circles.

4.3.3 $pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}$ bound state

Close to threshold, we can treat the $t\bar{t}$ -pair as a bound state with the structure of a colour-octet. If we consider the incoming partons to be a quark-antiquark-pair, the colour structure is equivalent to the process $q\bar{q} \rightarrow g$ and the products of colour-charge operators simplify to:

$$\mathcal{T}_n \cdot \mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}} = \frac{C_A}{2} - C_F, \quad (4.75)$$

$$\mathcal{T}_n \cdot \mathcal{T}_v = -\frac{C_A}{2}, \quad (4.76)$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{\bar{n}} \cdot \mathcal{T}_v = -\frac{C_A}{2}. \quad (4.77)$$

After setting the velocity β of the top- and antitop-quark to zero, we can write the two-particle correlations in the form:

$$\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow \text{octet}}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon) = C_A \left[2 \left(\frac{C_A}{2} - C_F \right) \tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon) - 2 \frac{C_A}{2} \tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \beta = 0) \right]. \quad (4.78)$$

We can compare our results to $s_{\bullet}^{(2)}$ from Ref. [7], which serves as an important check for our numerical values of $\tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ and $\tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}$. After performing a Laplace transform, we find:

$$\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow \text{octet}}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon) = 2^{4(1-\varepsilon)} e^{-4\gamma_E \varepsilon} \Gamma(-4\varepsilon) s_{\bullet}^{(2)}. \quad (4.79)$$

Our calculations do indeed match the analytical results in the first six significant figures and their values are:

$$\tilde{S}_{-4} = -8, \quad (4.80)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{-3} = 4.18071, \quad (4.81)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{-2} = -77.6107, \quad (4.82)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{-1} = -139.124, \quad (4.83)$$

$$\tilde{S}_0 = -451.786. \quad (4.84)$$

4.3.4 $pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}$

In order to calculate $\tilde{S}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \cos \vartheta, \beta)$ for hadronic $t\bar{t}$ -production, we first have to define the colour space basis c_I . We adopted the definitions by Ref. [27] for the basis

$$(c_1^{q\bar{q}})_{\{a\}} = \delta_{a_1 a_2} \delta_{a_3 a_4}, \quad (c_2^{q\bar{q}})_{\{a\}} = T_{a_2 a_1}^c T_{a_3 a_4}^c, \quad (4.85)$$

which results in a LO soft function looking like

$$\tilde{S}_{IJ}^{(0, q\bar{q})} = \frac{\langle c_I^{q\bar{q}} | c_J^{q\bar{q}} \rangle}{N}, \quad (4.86)$$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{S}^{(0, q\bar{q})} = \begin{pmatrix} N & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{C_F}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.87)$$

as well as colour matrices of the form:

$$(\omega_{ij}^{q\bar{q}})_{IJ} = \frac{1}{N} \langle c_I^{q\bar{q}} | \mathcal{T}_i \cdot \mathcal{T}_j | c_J^{q\bar{q}} \rangle. \quad (4.88)$$

There are three independent 2×2 matrices that are each symmetric:

$$\omega_{12}^{q\bar{q}} = \omega_{34}^{q\bar{q}} = -\frac{C_F}{4N} \begin{pmatrix} 4N^2 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.89)$$

$$\omega_{31}^{q\bar{q}} = \omega_{42}^{q\bar{q}} = -\frac{C_F}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & \left(2C_F - \frac{N}{2}\right) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.90)$$

$$\omega_{41}^{q\bar{q}} = \omega_{32}^{q\bar{q}} = \frac{C_F}{2N} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & N \\ N & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.91)$$

This means that we only need three different components to completely determine the real-virtual, hadronic two particle correlations $\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}$:

$$\left(\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})} \right)_{11} = \frac{C_A C_F}{N} \left[-2N^2 \tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon) - N^2 \tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \cos \vartheta, \beta) - N^2 \tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, -\cos \vartheta, \beta) \right], \quad (4.92)$$

$$\left(\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})} \right)_{12} = \frac{C_A C_F}{N} \left[-2\frac{N}{2} \tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \cos \vartheta, \beta) + 2\frac{N}{2} \tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, -\cos \vartheta, \beta) \right], \quad (4.93)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})} \right)_{22} &= \frac{C_A C_F}{N} \left[\frac{1}{2} \tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon) - 2\frac{N}{2} \left(2C_F - \frac{N}{2} \right) \tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \cos \vartheta, \beta) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 2\frac{1}{2} \tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, -\cos \vartheta, \beta) + \frac{1}{4} \tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, \cos \vartheta, \beta) + \frac{1}{4} \tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}(\varepsilon, -\cos \vartheta, \beta) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.94)$$

The results for all three independent components and their dependence on β as well as $\cos \vartheta$ for the zero-jettiness observable can be seen in Figures 4.4 to 4.9.

Figure 4.4: Plot of the colour matrix element $\left(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}\right)_{11}$ for the zero-jettiness observable with fixed $\cos \vartheta = 0.5$ and varying values of β . In order to improve visibility, $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-4}$, $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-3}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-2}$ have been multiplied by a factor of 10. The coefficient $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_0$ has a minimum at $\beta \approx 0.9$ which originates from the massive-massive building block.

Figure 4.5: Plot of the colour matrix element $\left(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}\right)_{11}$ for the zero-jettiness observable with fixed $\beta = 0.5$ and varying values of $\cos \vartheta$. In order to improve visibility, $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-4}$, $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-3}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-2}$ have been multiplied by a factor of 10. All coefficients are symmetric around the $\cos \vartheta = 0$ axis.

Figure 4.6: Plot of the colour matrix element $\left(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}\right)_{12}$ for the zero-jettiness observable with fixed $\cos \vartheta = 0.5$ and varying values of β . In order to improve visibility, $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-3}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-2}$ have been multiplied by a factor of 10. The coefficient $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-4}$ is equal to zero for all values of β .

Figure 4.7: Plot of the colour matrix element $\left(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}\right)_{12}$ for the zero-jettiness observable with fixed $\beta = 0.5$ and varying values of $\cos \vartheta$. In order to improve visibility, $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-3}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-2}$ have been multiplied by a factor of 10. The coefficient $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{-4}$ is equal to zero for all values of $\cos \vartheta$.

Figure 4.8: Plot of the colour matrix element $\left(\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}\right)_{22}$ for the zero-jettiness observable with fixed $\cos \vartheta = 0.5$ and varying values of β . In order to improve visibility, \tilde{S}_{-4} , \tilde{S}_{-3} , \tilde{S}_{-2} and \tilde{S}_{-1} have been multiplied by a factor of 10.

Figure 4.9: Plot of the colour matrix element $\left(\tilde{S}_{pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}}^{(2, \text{Re})}\right)_{22}$ for the zero-jettiness observable with fixed $\beta = 0.5$ and varying values of $\cos \vartheta$. In order to improve visibility, \tilde{S}_{-4} , \tilde{S}_{-3} , \tilde{S}_{-2} and \tilde{S}_{-1} have been multiplied by a factor of 10.

Summary and Outlook

In this thesis, we automated the calculation of two-particle correlations in NNLO real-virtual soft functions (see Eq. (4.35)), that involve massive partons, for general SCET-1 observables by extending the results from Refs. [4], [5] and [20].

At first, we calculated the soft matrix element in the massless-massless case ourselves (see Subsection 4.2.1) and obtained them from Refs. [24] and [25] in the massive-massive and massive-massless case. We then used symmetry arguments, involving the integral in Eq. (4.38), to determine the only building blocks, namely $\tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \text{Re})}$, $\tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ and $\tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ shown in Subsection 4.3.1, needed to calculate $\tilde{S}^{(2, \text{Re})}$.

In order to check the calculated numerical values for $\tilde{S}_{34}^{(2, \text{Re})}$, we compared our results to the ones of Ref. [6] and found them to be in excellent agreement with each other (see Fig. 4.3). A check of the other two building blocks, $\tilde{S}_{12}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ and $\tilde{S}_{31}^{(2, \text{Re})}$, which was achieved by comparing our values to ones in Ref. [7] for the threshold-resummation observable in a $pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}$ bound state process, likewise resulted in very good agreement.

With these checks completed, we changed over to calculating $\tilde{S}^{(2, \text{Re})}$ of the general hadronic $t\bar{t}$ -production process for the zero-jettiness observable, as it will be needed to expand the GENEVA Monte Carlo framework (see Ref. [8]) to $pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}$. The results can be seen in Figures 4.4 to 4.9.

Since the aim is to fully determine the total NNLO soft function in an effort to achieve NNLL' accuracy by utilizing RGEs, the next step will be to automate the calculations of three-particle correlations, as well as the double real-emission contributions for massive partons. This has already been achieved in the purely massless case, as can be seen Refs. [4] and [20].

Building Blocks

A.1 Massless-Massless

Figure A.1: Plot of the massless-massless building block for the threshold-resummation observable. There is no dependence on the velocity β or the angle $\cos\vartheta$ and the numerical values are displayed.

Figure A.2: Plot of the massless-massless building block for the zero-jettiness observable. There is no dependence on the velocity β or the angle ϑ and the numerical values are displayed.

A.2 Massive-Massless

Figure A.3: Plot of the massive-massless building block for the threshold-resummation observable. $\cos \vartheta$ is fixed to 0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95.

Figure A.4: Plot of the massive-massless building block for the threshold-resummation observable. $\cos \vartheta$ is fixed to -0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95 .

Figure A.5: Plot of the massive-massless building block for the threshold-resummation observable. β is fixed to 0.5 and $\cos \vartheta$ varies from -0.95 to 0.95.

Figure A.6: Plot of the massive-massless building block for the zero-jettiness observable. $\cos\vartheta$ is fixed to 0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95. The ε^0 coefficient reaches a maximum at $\beta \approx 0.9$.

Figure A.7: Plot of the massive-massless building block for the zero-jettiness observable. $\cos \vartheta$ is fixed to -0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95 . The ε^0 coefficient reaches a maximum at $\beta \approx 0.9$.

Figure A.8: Plot of the massive-massless building block for the zero-jettiness observable. β is fixed to 0.5 and $\cos\vartheta$ varies from -0.95 to 0.95.

A.3 Massive-Massive

Figure A.9: Plot of the massive-massive building block for the threshold-resummation observable. $\cos \vartheta$ is fixed to 0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95.

Figure A.10: Plot of the massive-massive building block for the threshold-resummation observable. $\cos \vartheta$ is fixed to -0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95 . The results are the same as for $\cos \vartheta = 0.5$, since there is no dependence on $\cos \vartheta$.

Figure A.11: Plot of the massive-massive building block for the threshold-resummation observable. β is fixed to 0.5 and the coefficients do not depend on $\cos \vartheta$.

Figure A.12: Plot of the massive-massive building block for the zero-jettiness observable. $\cos\vartheta$ is fixed to 0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95. The ε^0 coefficient reaches a maximum at $\beta \approx 0.9$.

Figure A.13: Plot of the massive-massive building block for the zero-jettiness observable. $\cos \vartheta$ is fixed to -0.5 and β varies from 0.05 to 0.95 . The results are the same as for $\cos \vartheta = 0.5$, since the dependence on $\cos \vartheta$ is symmetric around the $\cos \vartheta = 0$ axis. The ε^0 coefficient reaches a maximum at $\beta \approx 0.9$.

Figure A.14: Plot of the massive-massive building block for the zero-jettiness observable. β is fixed to 0.5 and the coefficients are symmetric in $\cos\vartheta$ around the $\cos\vartheta = 0$ axis.

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